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LEA G. SOLIS

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BARANGAY INTERVENTION PROGRAM FOR THE PREVENTION OF JUVENILES TO BECOMING CHILDREN IN CONFLICT WITH THE LAW

A Dissertation
Presented to the
Faculty of Graduate School
EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE
Manila, Philippines

In Partial Fulfillment
Of the Requirements for the Degree
Doctor of Philosophy in Criminology

LEA G. SOLIS
June 2024

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APPROVAL SHEET

In partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree, **Doctor of Philosophy in Criminal Justice**, this dissertation entitled: **“BARANGAY INTERVENTION PROGRAM FOR THE PREVENTION OF JUVENILES TO BECOMING CHILDREN IN CONFLICT WITH THE LAW”**, has been prepared and submitted by **Lea G. Solis**, is hereby recommended for approval.

DR. FRANCIA VIRTUDAZO
Adviser

Approved by the panel of examiners in partial fulfillment of the requirements in **Doctor of Philosophy in Criminal Justice**.

DR. HENRY L. LIGSON
Chair

DR. WILFREDO DALUGDOG
Member

DR. JIFFREY I. SAGURAN
Member

DR. ARMANDO E. ABEJUELA
Member

DR. JONIE MAMIGO
Member

Accepted and approved in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of **Doctor of Philosophy in Criminal Justice**.

LINO C. REYNOSO, Ph.D.
Dean, Graduate School

Date: _____

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DEDICATION

This paper is lovingly dedicated to

my husband Dr Dominador " Dennis " Solis

my sons Ricsie, Andy, and Andrew

my one and only daughter Alaenis

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LGS

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the juvenile delinquency in terms of the following: Children below the age of criminal responsibility, Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility, Repetition of offenses, Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes, and Joint Parental Responsibility. Likewise, Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours, Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs, Anti-Drug Campaigns, Provision of Livelihood Programs, Youth Leadership Training, Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities, and Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)

The data consistently highlights that juveniles are significantly influenced by their developmental stage and their environment, including peer pressure, family dynamics, and socio-economic conditions.

The study stresses the importance of community-based strategies and collaboration with NGOs in addressing juvenile delinquency and supporting community development.

The study reveals that there are no significant differences in perceptions of juvenile delinquency based on sex.

While specific aspects of juvenile delinquency do not show significant differences across age groups, the overall perceptions do vary notably.

The study finds no significant correlation between respondents' perceptions of juvenile delinquency and their views on the barangay's prevention practices.

The researcher proposed the following recommendations: 1) Implementation of recruitment strategies to ensure that both males and females are equally represented. Additionally, program planners should consider gender-specific needs and barriers to participation, ensuring that interventions are accessible and relevant to all genders; 2) Develop and implement multifaceted juvenile intervention programs that address both prevention and rehabilitation. Programs should focus on the unique developmental needs of juveniles, including mental, emotional, and psychological support; 3) Strengthening collaborations with NGOs and other community-based organizations; 4) Keep the youth engaged in positive pursuits, it is important to expand and diversify the range of activities available; 5) Establishing organized sports leagues, investing in community sports facilities, and developing varied recreational programs can help in keeping children and adolescents occupied and away from negative influences; 6) Introducing cultural and artistic programs, in addition to traditional sports, can cater to a broader range of interests and talents among the youth. These activities should be designed to foster a sense of community, responsibility, and personal growth; and 7) Comprehensive community outreach initiatives to raise awareness about child rights and the risks associated with drug use.

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INTRODUCTION

Understanding the root causes that bring children into conflict with the law (UNICEF). Children in conflict with the law are often those who face multiple and intersecting challenges in their lives. The

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United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF) confirms the multiplicity of risks that bring children into conflict with the law, and the importance of multi-sectoral responses that are tailored to a child’s individual circumstances.

Most young people who come into conflict with the law are struggling with multiple social and economic issues in their homes and/or communities. These issues range from being on the streets as a result of poverty and/or family dysfunction to coping with peer pressure in relation to risk-taking such as minor theft and substance abuse. Interventions need to be holistic to achieve maximum sustainable impacts. They must recognize the root causes of a child’s criminal behaviour and identify appropriate services to help the young person address the problems. Services needed may include support for basic education and skill training, employment, drug rehabilitation and family counselling.

Survival crimes and the link to child exploitation (2017).

When children breach the law in order to survive, formal contact with the criminal justice system is likely to deepen and prolong a child’s socio-economic exclusion. Acts of survival for which children may be criminalized include begging, theft, drug offences, and sex work (Anti-Slavery International, no date). A child-sensitive and rights-based approach precludes the attribution of criminal culpability, both on the basis of the principle that children be diverted from formal criminal justice involvement wherever possible, and because of the profound vulnerability of children engaging in survival crimes (including children who are

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trafficked or otherwise forced to engage in crime). The following excerpt describes the hardship that compels children to engage in “survival sex” in South Asia:

Children surviving on the streets alone, with their families or linked to the establishment where they work are more frequently found in large-sized South Asian cities. Homeless and disenfranchised, they lack basic care and may trade protection in exchange for favours, especially when they spend the night in the open on pavements, or in makeshift accommodations in squatter colonies, on footpaths, on railway platforms, at bus stations, below flyovers, at unprotected construction sites or workplaces. Survival sex is a frequent coping mechanism to procure food, drugs and entertainment opportunities.

Support for children in conflict with the law (2017). During emergencies, child protection actors report that numbers of child victims, witnesses and (alleged) offenders rise dramatically. Within conflict settings in particular, when justice systems are weakened through under-investment and lack of regulation, normal rules of detention are often misapplied or unenforced. Standards to ensure the wellbeing of juveniles in the justice system may be unmet or disregarded. In several countries, children displaced by conflict face a high risk of arrest and detention. Like other groups of vulnerable children, refugee and IDP children are at risk of spending longer periods in detention.

Of all the stages in a juvenile justice system, it is at first contact (arrest and immediately thereafter while in police custody) that the accused is most likely to be the victim of torture and other forms of cruel, inhuman and degrading treatment. Girls may be especially vulnerable to sexual harassment and abuse.

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Access may be more difficult in an emergency context because detaining authorities obstruct access to places of detention and interrogation, because the nature of the emergency makes access difficult or dangerous, or because there are too few actors on the ground. According to international standards, detention of a minor should be a measure of last resort, for the minimum necessary period, and should be limited to exceptional cases.

The criminal justice system is still used in many countries as a substitute for weak or incipient child protection institutions, generating approaches that further stigmatize socially excluded children, including those who have fled home as a result of violence or neglect, those who have been abandoned, and are homeless or poor, at times living or working on the street; and also those who suffer from mental health or substance abuse problems..

Depending on the jurisdiction, the provisions for detaining children for their own “protection” are found in juvenile justice legislation, child protection statute, or, decisions of this kind are operationalized through the discretion of police, judicial officials, and parole boards. Irrespective of whether the custodial term is framed as a justice decision or a protective measure the outcome is that children are held against their will and, in most cases, the institution in which the child is detained fails to provide the protective socio-ecology required for a child’s developmental well-being. The regularity with which this occurs, globally, reflects poorly on those charged with the care of children (whether parents, the State, or contracted caregivers) and it raises extremely confronting questions about the value that children hold in society more generally. The section that follows traces just

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some of the contexts in which children can be criminalized due to deficiencies in child protection systems; or discriminatory or punitive law and procedure.

REPUBLIC ACT NO. 10630, AN ACT STRENGTHENING THE JUVENILE JUSTICE SYSTEM IN THE PHILIPPINES, AMENDING FOR THE PURPOSE REPUBLIC ACT NO. 9344, OTHERWISE KNOWN AS THE "JUVENILE JUSTICE AND WELFARE ACT OF 2006" AND APPROPRIATING FUNDS THEREFORE

"SEC. 20. *Children Below the Age of Criminal Responsibility.* – If it has been determined that the child taken into custody is fifteen (15) years old or below, the authority which will have an initial contact with the child, in consultation with the local social welfare and development officer, has the duty to immediately release the child to the custody of his/her parents or guardian, or in the absence thereof, the child's nearest relative. The child shall be subjected to a community-based intervention program supervised by the local social welfare and development officer, unless the best interest of the child requires the referral of the child to a youth care facility or 'Bahay Pag-asa' managed by LGUs or licensed and/or accredited NGOs monitored by the DSWD.

"The local social welfare and development officer shall determine the appropriate programs for the child who has been released, in consultation with the child and the person having custody over the child. If the parents, guardians or nearest relatives cannot be located, or if they refuse to take custody, the child may be released to any of the following:

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"(a) A duly registered nongovernmental or religious organization;

"(b) A barangay official or a member of the Barangay Council for the Protection of Children (BCPC);

"(c) A local social welfare and development officer; or, when and where appropriate, the DSWD.

"If the child has been found by the local social welfare and development officer to be dependent, abandoned, neglected or abused by his/her parents and the best interest of the child requires that he/she be placed in a youth care facility or 'Bahay Pag-asa', the child's parents or guardians shall execute a written authorization for the voluntary commitment of the child: *Provided*, That if the child has no parents or guardians or if they refuse or fail to execute the written authorization for voluntary commitment, the proper petition for involuntary commitment shall be immediately filed by the DSWD or the Local Social Welfare and Development Office (LSWDO) pursuant to Presidential Decree No. 603, as amended, otherwise known as 'The Child and Youth Welfare Code' and the Supreme Court rule on commitment of children: *Provided, further*, That the minimum age for children committed to a youth care facility or 'Bahay Pag-asa' shall be twelve (12) years old."

"SEC. 20-A. *Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt From Criminal Responsibility.* – A child who is above twelve (12) years of age up to fifteen (15) years of age and who commits parricide, murder, infanticide, kidnapping and serious illegal detention where the victim is killed or raped, robbery, with homicide or rape, destructive arson, rape, or carnapping where the

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driver or occupant is killed or raped or offenses under Republic Act No. 9165 (Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002) punishable by more than twelve (12) years of imprisonment, shall be deemed a neglected child under Presidential Decree No. 603, as amended, and shall be mandatorily placed in a special facility within the youth care faculty or 'Bahay Pag-asa' called the Intensive Juvenile Intervention and Support Center (IJISC).

"In accordance with existing laws, rules, procedures and guidelines, the proper petition for involuntary commitment and placement under the IJISC shall be filed by the local social welfare and development officer of the LGU where the offense was committed, or by the DSWD social worker in the local social welfare and development officer's absence, within twenty-four (24) hours from the time of the receipt of a report on the alleged commission of said child. The court, where the petition for involuntary commitment has been filed shall decide on the petition within seventy-two (72) hours from the time the said petition has been filed by the DSWD/LSWDO. The court will determine the initial period of placement of the child within the IJISC which shall not be less than one (1) year. The multi-disciplinary team of the IJISC will submit to the court a case study and progress report, to include a psychiatric evaluation report and recommend the reintegration of the child to his/her family or the extension of the placement under the IJISC. The multi-disciplinary team will also submit a report to the court on the services extended to the parents and family of the child and the compliance of the parents in the intervention program. The court will decide whether the child has successfully completed the center-based intervention program and is already prepared to be

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reintegrated with his/her family or if there is a need for the continuation of the center-based rehabilitation of the child. The court will determine the next period of assessment or hearing on the commitment of the child."

"SEC. 20-B. *Repetition of Offenses.* – A child who is above twelve (12) years of age up to fifteen (15) years of age and who commits an offense for the second time or oftener: *Provided,* That the child was previously subjected to a community-based intervention program, shall be deemed a neglected child under Presidential Decree No. 603, as amended, and shall undergo an intensive intervention program supervised by the local social welfare and development officer: *Provided, further,* That, if the best interest of the child requires that he/she be placed in a youth care facility or 'Bahay Pag-asa', the child's parents or guardians shall execute a written authorization for the voluntary commitment of the child: *Provided, finally,* That if the child has no parents or guardians or if they refuse or fail to execute the written authorization for voluntary commitment, the proper petition for involuntary commitment shall be immediately filed by the DSWD or the LSWDO pursuant to Presidential Decree No. 603, as amended."

"SEC. 20-C. *Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes.* – Any person who, in the commission of a crime, makes use, takes advantage of, or profits from the use of children, including any person who abuses his/her authority over the child or who, with abuse of confidence, takes advantage of the vulnerabilities of the child and shall induce, threaten or instigate the commission of the crime, shall be imposed the penalty prescribed by law for the crime committed in its maximum period."

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"SEC. 20-D. *Joint Parental Responsibility.* – Based on the recommendation of the multi-disciplinary team of the IJISC, the LSWDO or the DSWD, the court may require the parents of a child in conflict with the law to undergo counseling or any other intervention that, in the opinion of the court, would advance the welfare and best interest of the child. "As used in this Act, 'parents' shall mean any of the following: "(a) Biological parents of the child; or "(b) Adoptive parents of the child; or "(c) Individuals who have custody of the child. "A court exercising jurisdiction over a child in conflict with the law may require the attendance of one or both parents of the child at the place where the proceedings are to be conducted.

"The parents shall be liable for damages unless they prove, to the satisfaction of the court, that they were exercising reasonable supervision over the child at the time the child committed the offense and exerted reasonable effort and utmost diligence to prevent or discourage the child from committing another offense."

"SEC. 20-E. *Assistance to Victims of Offenses Committed by Children.* – The victim of the offense committed by a child and the victim's family shall be provided the appropriate assistance and psychological intervention by the LSWDO, the DSWD and other concerned agencies."

Juvenile delinquency is the term used to describe adolescents who participate in unlawful activity or antisocial behavior, which frequently results in their involvement with the law. Fostering a secure and nurturing environment for kids and teenagers requires an understanding of and commitment to preventing

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juvenile delinquency. The three main strategies used to prevent children from getting into legal trouble are early intervention, community involvement, and educational programs. These initiatives seek to address risk factors that may fuel delinquent conduct, such as dysfunctional families, financial hardships, and difficulties in the classroom. Communities can encourage good development, resilience, and eventually lower the chance of children entering the criminal justice system by putting targeted solutions like mentorship programs, counseling services, and educational assistance into place.

In the Philippines, community-based programs called barangay prevention programs are designed to address a range of socioeconomic concerns at the local level. These initiatives aim to raise general community welfare, promote public health, and deter crime. In the Philippines, a "barangay" is the smallest unit of government, akin to a town or neighborhood. Under the direction of elected authorities, every barangay functions somewhat independently, which qualifies them to carry out localized preventative initiatives. In order to accomplish their objectives, these programs are frequently customized to the unique requirements and difficulties of the community, making use of available resources and citizen participation.

Preventing crime is one of the main goals of barangay preventive programs. These programs are a part of a larger endeavor to improve community safety and lower the frequency of criminal activity. Neighborhood watch programs, more barangay tanod (local peacekeeper) patrols, and community-based crime prevention education are regular activities. Many barangays also form alliances

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with neighborhood police departments in an effort to enhance reaction times and efficacy in dealing with criminal activity. In addition, the programs frequently include community service and reintegration assistance as means of rehabilitating criminals and preventing recidivism.

Additional essential elements of barangay prevention programs are public health and safety. These programs seek to protect inhabitants' health and well-being, encourage good cleanliness and health habits, and stop the spread of illness. Vaccination drives, cleanliness programs, and health information seminars are typical activities. Numerous barangays were instrumental in putting quarantine orders into effect, distributing personal protective equipment (PPE), and assisting with immunization campaigns during the COVID-19 epidemic. In addition, barangays frequently provide training on disaster preparedness and response to provide locals the abilities they need to deal with the regular natural disasters that occur in the Philippines.

Barangay Prevention Programs concentrate on more general facets of welfare and community development in addition to crime and health. This covers initiatives for education, youth participation, and poverty alleviation. For example, barangays may set up livelihood training programs to equip locals with the skills required for jobs or starting their own business. Scholarships and after-school tutoring are two popular forms of educational support services. In addition, youth engagement programs like sports leagues and cultural events support the development of a feeling of community and keep young people away from

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delinquent behavior. These initiatives support the community's resilience and long-term growth in addition to meeting its urgent needs.

The success of Barangay Prevention Programs often hinges on the collaborative efforts between local government units, non-governmental organizations, and the community members themselves. By involving residents in the planning and implementation of these programs, barangays ensure that the initiatives are relevant and effective. This participatory approach also fosters a sense of ownership and accountability among community members, which is crucial for the sustainability of these programs. Additionally, many barangays seek support from external partners, such as international aid organizations and private sector donors, to enhance their capacity and resources. Through these collaborative efforts, Barangay Prevention Programs have become vital in promoting safety, health, and development at the grassroots level in the Philippines.

Youth Involved with the Juvenile Justice System

Some children and youth become involved with the juvenile justice system because they are accused of committing a delinquent or criminal act. Other youth encounter the system for status offenses—actions that are illegal only because of a youth's age—such as truancy, underage drinking, and running away from home. Not all of these cases, however, are formally processed through the courts.

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While an estimated 2.7 million youth under the age of 18 were arrested in the United States during a single year in 1997, that number decreased by 74 percent in 2019.

Though overall rates have been steadily declining over the past years, approximately 423,077 delinquency cases are adjudicated and disposed in juvenile courts annually. Fifty-two percent (220,000) of those disposed cases were adjudicated delinquent in 2018.

Figure 1.

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Youth are referred to the juvenile justice system for different types of offenses. Figure 1 illustrates the percent of referrals based on the types of offenses for youth between the ages of 12 and 17 in 2018.

While many youth cases do not get processed formally through the court, the majority of youth that are processed through the juvenile court are adjudicated (i. e., declared by a judge to be) delinquent, for most offenses.

An average of 53 percent of all petitioned cases that went to juvenile court were adjudicated delinquent in 2019. Fifty-one percent of person offenses were adjudicated delinquent, 53 percent of property offenses, 51 percent of drug offences, and 56 percent of public order offenses.

Between 1997 and 2019, the number of youth detained in residential placement decreased 50 percent to a total of 14,344, and the number of youth committed in residential placement decreased 73 percent to 21,141. The total number of youth in residential placement in 2019 was 36,479, its lowest level since the data collection began in 1997, when 105,055 youth were held in out-of-home placement.

The average state cost for the secure confinement of a young person is now \$588 per day, or \$214,620 per year, a 44 percent increase from 2014. These cost figures over a six-year period represent the growing economic impact of incarcerating youth. However, the long-term impact of these policies extends well beyond the fiscal cost.

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Youth who are detained or incarcerated may be subject to various negative circumstances, including: overcrowding, physical and sexual violence, risk of suicide, and death.

Limiting incarceration as a punitive measure for youth when applicable has strong potential to mitigate some of these negative circumstances that occur in or are exacerbated by various out-of-home placement settings.

Background of the Study

Juvenile Justice System in the Philippines: Rehabilitation and Reintegration (2023)

The juvenile justice system in the Philippines is designed to prioritize the rehabilitation and reintegration of young offenders. Recognizing that young people who commit offenses should be given the opportunity to reform and become law-abiding citizens, the government has implemented the Juvenile Justice and Welfare Act of 2006 (Republic Act No. 9344). This law aims to protect the rights of children in conflict with the law and promote their rehabilitation and reintegration into society.

An Alternative Approach In the Philippines, the primary approach in dealing with children in conflict with the law is a diversion. Diversion seeks to address the underlying issues that contribute to their offending behavior without resorting to formal court proceedings. Instead, community-based interventions

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such as counseling, mediation, and rehabilitation programs are provided. The goal is to prevent children from entering the formal justice system and to offer them appropriate support and guidance.

Specialized Services When diversion is not appropriate or unsuccessful, the Juvenile Justice and Welfare Act provides for the establishment of special youth courts, known as Family Courts. These courts follow a different set of procedures and provide specialized services for children in conflict with the law. They offer comprehensive assessments, rehabilitation programs, educational support, and vocational training to address the specific needs of young offenders.

In the event that a child is found guilty of an offense, the court may impose a range of dispositions or interventions aimed at their rehabilitation. These include probation, community service, counseling, education, vocational training, and other appropriate interventions. The focus is on addressing the underlying causes of the offending behavior and promoting the child's reintegration into society as a productive and law-abiding citizen.

The Juvenile Justice and Welfare Act emphasizes that detention should only be used as a last resort and for the shortest appropriate period. Secure and non-secure residential care facilities may be used, but efforts are made to ensure that the conditions are conducive to the child's well-being and rehabilitation. The law also mandates separate facilities for children to ensure their safety and protection.

The involvement of the family and the community is crucial in the rehabilitation and reintegration process. The Juvenile Justice and Welfare Act

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recognizes the important role of the family in supporting the child's development and reintegration into society. Additionally, community-based organizations and programs are encouraged to participate in the rehabilitation process, providing additional support and opportunities for young offenders.

In recent years, the Philippines has been actively working towards strengthening and improving its juvenile justice system. Efforts have been made to enhance the capacity of justice system stakeholders, develop more effective diversion programs, and provide comprehensive services for children in conflict with the law. These initiatives aim to ensure better outcomes for young offenders and increase the chances of successful rehabilitation and reintegration.

The juvenile justice system in the Philippines is firmly rooted in the principles of rehabilitation and reintegration. Through diversion programs, specialized Family Courts, appropriate dispositions, and the involvement of the family and community, the country is making strides in reforming young offenders and helping them become productive members of society. Ongoing efforts to strengthen and improve the system ensure that children in conflict with the law receive the support and guidance they need to lead law-abiding lives and contribute positively to their communities.

Protection of children at risk and children in conflict with the law during COVID-19. The Joining Forces Alliance calls on all local government units to comply with the Joint Memorandum Circular by Department of Interior and Local Governance (DILG) and the Council for the Welfare of Children (CWC) dated April 6, 2020 in the context of the ECQ.

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INTERVENTION PROGRAMS FOR CHILD-IN-CONFLICT WITH THE LAW (CICL): THE CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED WITH ITS IMPLEMENTATION (Marcel B. Atianzar, 2022)

With the laws enacted for the protection of the child, there are still challenges that are met along the way. This study determined the challenges in the implementation of intervention program for Children-in Conflict with the Law (CICL) in the local context. A total of fifty-eight (58) Social Workers and their copartner social workers in the Barangays took part in this study. A self-made questionnaire was utilized to ascertain the challenges encountered in the implementation of the intervention program for CICL. Descriptive method of research was utilized to answer the objectives of the study. Results revealed that the main challenge in the implementation of the intervention program are the behavior of CICL and their parents towards the intervention program, hence, building rapport both with the CICL and the parents during the initial phase of the helping relationship should be established.

The child in conflict with the law (CICL) are youthful offenders known also as chronic juvenile offenders, chronic delinquents, or chronic recidivists. These are the youth who had been arrested four or more times during their minority and had perpetuated a striking majority of serious criminal acts (Seigel, Welsh & Senna, 2006).

Article 40 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) stipulated that the State recognizes the right of every child alleged as, accused of, adjudged, or recognized as having infringed the penal law to be

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treated in a manner consistent with the promotion of the child's sense of dignity and worth, taking into account the child's age and desirability of promoting his/her reintegration. In the Philippines, under Republic Act 9344 otherwise known as Juvenile Justice Welfare Act of 2006 defines that a Child in Conflict with the Law refers to a child who is alleged as, accused of, or adjudged as, having committed an offense under Philippine laws.

Republic Act 10630 strengthened the Philippine Juvenile Justice System; it kept the indemnity from criminal liability of children aged fifteen (15) years old. However, a child who is above 12 years of age up to 15 years of age who commits serious offenses that are punishable by more than 12 years shall be mandatorily placed in an Intensive Juvenile Intervention and Support Center. Repeat offenders, or children who have committed crimes more than three times, would also be considered as neglected children and, as such, must undergo intervention programs supervised by the local social welfare and development officers.

Conceptual Framework

This study will be anchored on the REPUBLIC ACT NO. 10630 AN ACT STRENGTHENING THE JUVENILE JUSTICE SYSTEM IN THE PHILIPPINES FOR THE PURPOSE OF AMENDING REPUBLIC ACT NO. 9344, OTHERWISE KNOWN AS THE "JUVENILE JUSTICE AND WELFARE ACT OF 2006" AND APPROPRIATING FUNDS THEREFOR

Section 6. Section 20 of Republic Act No. 9344 is hereby amended to read as follows:

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"SEC. 20. *Children Below the Age of Criminal Responsibility.* – If it has been determined that the child taken into custody is fifteen (15) years old or below, the authority which will have an initial contact with the child, in consultation with the local social welfare and development officer, has the duty to immediately release the child to the custody of his/her parents or guardian, or in the absence thereof, the child's nearest relative. The child shall be subjected to a community-based intervention program supervised by the local social welfare and development officer, unless the best interest of the child requires the referral of the child to a youth care facility or 'Bahay Pag-asa' managed by LGUs or licensed and/or accredited NGOs monitored by the DSWD.

"SEC. 20-A. *Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt From Criminal Responsibility.* – A child who is above twelve (12) years of age up to fifteen (15) years of age and who commits parricide, murder, infanticide, kidnapping and serious illegal detention where the victim is killed or raped, robbery, with homicide or rape, destructive arson, rape, or carjacking where the driver or occupant is killed or raped or offenses under Republic Act No. 9165 (Comprehensive Dangerous Drugs Act of 2002) punishable by more than twelve (12) years of imprisonment, shall be deemed a neglected child under Presidential Decree No. 603, as amended, and shall be mandatorily placed in a special facility within the youth care facility or 'Bahay Pag-asa' called the Intensive Juvenile Intervention and Support Center (IJISC).

"SEC. 20-B. *Repetition of Offenses.* – A child who is above twelve (12) years of age up to fifteen (15) years of age and who commits an offense for the

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second time or oftener: *Provided*, That the child was previously subjected to a community-based intervention program, shall be deemed a neglected child under Presidential Decree No. 603, as amended, and shall undergo an intensive intervention program supervised by the local social welfare and development officer: *Provided, further*, That, if the best interest of the child requires that he/she be placed in a youth care facility or 'Bahay Pag-asa', the child's parents or guardians shall execute a written authorization for the voluntary commitment of the child: *Provided, finally*, That if the child has no parents or guardians or if they refuse or fail to execute the written authorization for voluntary commitment, the proper petition for involuntary commitment shall be immediately filed by the DSWD or the LSWDO pursuant to Presidential Decree No. 603, as amended."

"SEC. 20-C. *Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes.* – Any person who, in the commission of a crime, makes use, takes advantage of, or profits from the use of children, including any person who abuses his/her authority over the child or who, with abuse of confidence, takes advantage of the vulnerabilities of the child and shall induce, threaten or instigate the commission of the crime, shall be imposed the penalty prescribed by law for the crime committed in its maximum period."

"SEC. 20-D. *Joint Parental Responsibility.* – Based on the recommendation of the multi-disciplinary team of the IJISC, the LSWDO or the DSWD, the court may require the parents of a child in conflict with the law to undergo counseling or any other intervention that, in the opinion of the court, would advance the welfare and best interest of the child.

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Likewise, this study will be utilized the REVISED RULE ON CHILDREN IN CONFLICT WITH THE LAW. Section 42. *Determination of the Best Interests of the Child.* – The following factors may be considered in determining the best interests of a child in conflict with the law: the child's age and sex, the child's mental and physical health, the mental and physical health of the parents, their lifestyle and other social factors; the emotional ties between the parents and the child, the ability of the parents to provide the child with food, shelter, clothing and medical care; the established living pattern for the child concerning school, home, community and religious institution, quality of schooling, the existence of other relatives who may be in a better position to be with the child and the child's relationship with these relatives; the child's background, maturity and level of understanding, sexual orientation, lifestyle and any other characteristics and needs of the child that the court may deem relevant.

Likewise, Barangay Prevention Practices to Prevent Children from Becoming in Conflict with the Law as follows:

Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities. Ensure the safety of children by regularly monitoring their activities within the community.

Implementation of Curfew Hours. Enforce curfew hours for minors to prevent them from engaging in activities that may lead to legal trouble.

Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs. Establish community-based rehabilitation programs for children who have shown signs of problematic behavior.

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Anti-Drug Campaigns. Conduct regular anti-drug campaigns to educate children and the community about the dangers of drug use.

Provision of Livelihood Programs. Offer livelihood programs to parents and guardians to alleviate economic pressures that may lead to neglect or child involvement in illegal activities.

Youth Leadership Training. Organize youth leadership training programs to develop a sense of responsibility and leadership among children and teenagers.

Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities. Encourage children to participate in sports and recreational activities to promote physical health and teamwork.

Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). Partner with NGOs that focus on child welfare to implement additional programs and services aimed at preventing juvenile delinquency.

These practices aim to create a supportive and safe environment for children, reducing the risk of them becoming involved in criminal activities.

Research Framework

Figure 2 is the research paradigm of this study. The first rectangular shape represents the Barangay personnel of respondents

The first rectangular shape inside the big box is Juvenile Delinquency in terms of Children below the age of criminal responsibility, Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility, Repetition

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of offenses, Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes, and Joint Parental Responsibility

The second rectangular shape is the Barangays Prevention Practices in terms of Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours, Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs, Anti-Drug Campaigns, Provision of Livelihood Programs, Youth Leadership Training, Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities, and Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs).

The significant difference and in the assessment of respondents is the dotted lines. While the arrow on the opposite direction represents the significant relationship in the assessment of the two groups of respondents between the Juvenile Delinquency and Baragay's Prevention Practices.

The ultimate objective of this study is to come up with a proposed Barangay interventions program.

Figure 2. Research Paradigm

Statement of the Problem

This study assessed the juvenile delinquency and Barangay prevention practices to becoming children in conflict with the law. Specifically, it answered the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of respondents in terms of the following:

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- 1.1 age, and
- 1.2 sex?
2. What is the assessment of the Barangay Personnel respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 Children below the age of criminal responsibility,
 - 2.2 Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility
 - 2.3 Repetition of offenses
 - 2.4 Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes
 - 2.5 Joint Parental Responsibility?
3. Is there significant difference in the assessment of the respondents on the Juvenile delinquency?
4. What is the assessment of the Barangay Personnel respondents on the Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of the following:
 - 4.1 Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities,
 - 4.2 Implementation of Curfew Hours,
 - 4.3 Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs
 - 4.4 Anti-Drug Campaigns,
 - 4.5 Provision of Livelihood Programs,
 - 4.6 Youth Leadership Training,
 - 4.7 Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities,
 - 4.8 Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)

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5. Is there significant difference in the assessment of the] respondents on the Barangay's Prevention Practices

6. Is there significant relationship in the assessment of the two (2) groups of respondents between the juvenile delinquency and Barangay's Prevention Practices?

7. Based on the results of the study what Barangay interventions program can be proposed?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the assessment of the respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of the following: Children below the age of criminal responsibility, Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility, Repetition of offenses, Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes, and Joint Parental Responsibility.

2. There is no significant difference in the assessment of the respondents on the Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours, Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs, Anti-Drug Campaigns, Provision of Livelihood Programs, Youth Leadership Training, Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities, and Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)

3. There is no significant relationship in the assessment of respondents between the juvenile delinquency and Barangay's Prevention Practices?

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Significance of the Study

The results of this study would be very crucial and of great significance to the following stakeholders:

To the *Government*, the findings of this study may be exploited by the government legislators and executives to explore further on the Barangay interventions program.

To the *Students of the Graduate Schools*, the literature and studies reviewed, as well as the theories and methodologies applied in this research may be of great help to them in the furtherance of their respective studies in Criminology.

To this *Researcher*, once this researcher is able to successfully defend her dissertation before the panel of experts, she would be able to fulfill her dreams , that in one way or the other, she can contribute in her own little way at improving the juvenile delinquency and Barangay's Prevention Practices.

To the *Future Researchers*, should they conduct researches of similar or identical constructs and perspectives, the literature and studies, as well as the methodologies included in this research studies may be useful to them.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

This study conducted at selected Barangays in Quezon City and assessed the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of the Children below the age of criminal

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responsibility, Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility, Repetition of offenses;, Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes, and Joint Parental Responsibility. Likewise, on the Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours, Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs, Anti-Drug Campaigns, Provision of Livelihood Programs, Youth Leadership Training, Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities, and Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs).

METHODOOGY

Research Design

The researcher utilized the evaluation survey research design. Creswell, John W. and J. David, Creswell. 2018, explain that evaluation research study is a "process used to determine and identify the purpose of the survey research and accordingly, the primary purpose is to answer questions about variables of interest to the researcher. Since the main objective of the study is to assess the the

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juvenile delinquency and student's prevention practices to becoming children in conflict with the law. On the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of the following: Children below the age of criminal responsibility, Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility, Repetition of offenses, Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes, and Joint Parental Responsibility. For the Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of the on the Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours, Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs, Anti-Drug Campaigns, Provision of Livelihood Programs, Youth Leadership Training, Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities, and Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs).

Research Locale

The locale of the study conducted selected Barangay namely: Barangays Sta. Lucia, San Bartolome, and Bagbag. During the actual conduct of survey, the respondents were likewise in the same place where the barangays are located. The respondents were purposively selected. Said respondents were those who are directly involved and have knowledge about the juvenile delinquency.

A survey method is the preferred type of approach for this study. In this case, it can be beneficial to acknowledge the advantages of survey designs, using the assessments of the respondents who have direct knowledge about the juvenile delinquency and Barangay's prevention practices to becoming children in conflict with the law.

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Research Instrument

As part of the data collection, the researcher's made a survey questionnaire to assess respondents on the juvenile delinquency and Barangay's prevention practices to becoming children in conflict with the law.

An introductory letter to the respondents were likewise be prepared, requesting them to answer all the items needed to completely gather the data required. The letter will also explain the objective of the study to the respondents. The main body of the survey questionnaire was consisted of the variables and indicators/statements concerning the the assessment of respondents on the juvenile delinquency and barangay's prevention practices to becoming children in conflict with the law. On the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of the following: Children below the age of criminal responsibility, Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility, Repetition of offenses, Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes, and Joint Parental Responsibility. For the Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of the Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours, Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs, Anti-Drug Campaigns, Provision of Livelihood Programs, Youth Leadership Training, Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities, and Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs).

The following rating scales were used by the respondents in their assessments:

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<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Degree</u>
4	3.51-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)/Highly Practiced (HP)
3	2.51-3.50	Agree (A)/Practiced (P)
2	1.51-2.50	Disagree (DA)/ Less Practiced (LP)
1	1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Practiced (NP)

Population, Sample, and Sampling Technique

The population and sampling procedure (Babbie, 2015; & Fowler, 2014 cited by Creswell, John W. and J. David, Creswell, 2018) provide for the essential aspects of the population and sample describe in a research plan. A total of 90 respondents employed in this study. 30 participants for 3 Barangays.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the gathering of data, the researcher initially wrote a letter to the Barangay Officials. The respective approval of those personnel in charge is extremely necessary. After their respective approval, the questionnaires were distributed to and retrieved from selected respondents by the researcher.

Upon the distribution of the questionnaires to the individual respondents, the researcher may make some explanations to the participants on the objective of the study as well as how they would fill up the same. Thereafter, the respondents were given a week to complete the questionnaire and send it back to the researcher. After a week, the researcher made personal calls or messages for follow-ups to the different locations where the respondents are having their respective offices to retrieve the filled-up survey instruments.

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Statistical Treatment of Data

The collected data were tallied, classified, and tabulated. Listed in the columns are the responses per item of the questionnaire and the rows representing the respondents. Data responses coming from the respondents were considered for statistical analysis using the following statistical tools.

Weighted Mean. The weighted mean scores were computed to measure the assessment of the respondents. To obtain the weighted mean scores, the computed weighted mean scores on juvenile delinquency and Barangay's prevention practices to becoming children in conflict with the law were interpreted using the following scales:

<u>Scale</u>	<u>Range</u>	<u>Degree</u>
4	3.51-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)/Highly Practiced (HP)
3	2.51-3.50	Agree (A)/Practiced (P)
2	1.51-2.50	Disagree (DA)/ Less Practiced (LP)
1	1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Practiced (NP)

ANOVA. To test the hypotheses of no significant difference in the assessment of the Barangay personnel respondents, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were utilized.

Pearson's r for the significant relationship in the assessment of the respondents between the juvenile delinquency and Barangay's prevention practices to becoming children in conflict with the law.

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Ethical Considerations

In the conduct of the study, the researcher considered the following ethical considerations.

1. Respondents were briefed fully on the purpose of the conduct of the research.
2. It was made very clear to the respondents that participation is voluntary.
3. Data collection and analysis will be described clearly to them so that they know what they are doing.
4. Respondents were given an informed consent letter.
5. Confidentiality of the information will be maintained by protecting the anonymity of the respondents

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

1. *On the demographic profile of respondents.*

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution on the demographic profile of respondents.

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	25-35 years old	33	33%
	36-45 years old	23	23%

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	46-55 years old	24	24%
	Above 55years old	20	20%
Total		100	100%
Sex	Male	70	70%
	Female	30	30%
Total		100	100%

The above table 1 outlines the demographic characteristics of survey respondents, categorized by age and sex.

Age Distribution. The respondents are divided into four age groups. The group aged 25-35 years has the highest representation, with 33 individuals making up 33% of the total respondents. This is followed closely by those aged 46-55 and 36-45, who represent 24% and 23% of the total, respectively. The least represented are those aged 55 and above, accounting for 20% of the sample. This distribution shows a reasonable spread across different adult age groups, though it leans slightly younger.

Sex: The division based on sex shows a significant skew, with males representing 70% of the respondents and females only 30%. This imbalance suggests that the results of the survey might be more reflective of the perspectives and experiences of male participants than of females.

The data indicates that while there is a broad age range represented, the gender distribution is quite uneven. This imbalance can impact the survey results, potentially leading to conclusions that are more biased towards male perspectives. When interpreting findings from this survey, it is essential to consider this skew as it might influence the generalizability of the results to the wider population. For

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future surveys, aiming for a more balanced gender ratio could help in achieving more comprehensive insights that are applicable across different demographics.

2. On the assessment of the Barangay Personnel respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of the following: Children below the age of criminal responsibility, Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility Repetition of offenses, Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes, and Joint Parental Responsibility.

Table 2 presents the Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of Children below the age of criminal responsibility

**Table 2
Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of Children below the age of criminal responsibility**

Children below the age of criminal responsibility	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal and Adjectival Interpretation
Children below the age of criminal responsibility are recognized as still developing mentally, emotionally, and psychologically	2.680	0.815	Agree -Practiced
They may not fully understand the consequences of their actions or have the ability to make informed decisions	2.930	0.844	Agree -Practiced
More susceptible to exploitation and involvement in illegal activities	3.040	0.994	Agree -Practiced
Young children are highly impressionable and may be influenced by peer pressure, media, or adults in their environment	2.770	0.941	Agree -Practiced
They may engage in risky or delinquent behavior without fully comprehending the implications	2.700	0.785	Agree -Practiced
Children below the age of criminal responsibility may have limited cognitive abilities and judgment skills	2.770	0.839	Agree -Practiced

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They may act impulsively without considering the consequences or fully understanding the moral and legal implications of their actions	2.770	0.851	Agree -Practiced
They rely heavily on adults, such as parents, guardians, or caregivers, for guidance, support, and supervision	2.760	0.976	Agree -Practiced
Potential for positive change and rehabilitation in these young individuals	2.500	0.969	Disagree-Partially Practiced
They are entitled to special safeguards and interventions aimed at promoting their well-being and preventing their involvement in criminal activities	2.690	0.748	Agree -Practiced
Overall Mean	2.761	0.390	Agree -Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

Table 2 presents an analysis of survey responses concerning the perceptions of juvenile delinquency in children below the age of criminal responsibility. The data is organized around various indicators that assess mental, emotional, and psychological maturity, alongside susceptibility to negative influences and understanding of legal consequences. Each indicator is quantified using a weighted mean and standard deviation, followed by a verbal and adjectival interpretation.

The overall consensus, indicated by the verbal interpretations predominantly marked as "Agree - Practiced," suggests that respondents recognize that children below the age of criminal responsibility are still developing and may not fully comprehend the ramifications of their actions. For instance, indicators like the influence of peer pressure and media, as well as the susceptibility to exploitation, scored around 3.0, indicating a general agreement that these factors significantly affect juvenile behavior. The standard deviations, relatively modest across most indicators, imply a general uniformity in responses, pointing to a broad agreement among the respondents.

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However, there is a notable divergence in views regarding the potential for positive change and rehabilitation in these young individuals, which scored a 2.50, categorized as "Disagree-Partially Practiced." This suggests a more divided opinion on the effectiveness or current practice of rehabilitation efforts for juveniles, which contrasts with the more agreed-upon views about their developmental challenges and influences.

The overall mean of 2.761 falling within the "Agree - Practiced" range reinforces the notion that there is a solid agreement on most aspects of juvenile delinquency concerning young children, except for their rehabilitation potential. This discrepancy invites a closer examination of current juvenile justice practices and perhaps signals a need for more focused interventions that enhance the rehabilitative aspects of juvenile justice systems to better cater to the developmental needs and rehabilitation potential of young offenders.

Table 3 presents the Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who re Exempt from Criminal Responsibility

Table 3
Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility

Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Serious crimes may involve acts of violence, including assault, physical fights, or even acts of homicide	3.040	1.034	Agree -Practiced
May engage in serious sexual offenses, such as rape or sexual assault	3.150	0.903	Agree -Practiced
Serious property crimes committed by children may include burglary, robbery, arson, or vandalism	2.890	0.815	Agree -Practiced
May participate in serious criminal activities, including drug trafficking, extortion, or organized violence	2.700	1.040	Agree -Practiced

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Some children may illegally possess or use weapons, such as firearms or knives, to intimidate others or commit acts of violence	2.960	0.695	Agree -Practiced
Children may be influenced by peer pressure, family dynamics, or socioeconomic factors that contribute to involvement in drug-related activities	3.210	0.967	Agree -Practiced
May involve the possession, distribution, or trafficking of illegal drugs	2.790	0.957	Agree -Practiced
Repeatedly engage in serious criminal behavior may demonstrate a pattern of delinquency that requires comprehensive intervention strategies.	2.770	1.014	Agree -Practiced
Children may be exploited or coerced into participating in organized crime activities, such as human trafficking, smuggling, or gang operations.	3.080	0.907	Agree -Practiced
Children who commit serious crimes may themselves be victims of abuse, neglect, or trauma	2.930	0.832	Agree -Practiced
Overall Mean	2.952	0.362	Agree -Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

Table 3 assesses respondents' perceptions of serious crimes committed by children who are exempt from criminal responsibility. The data is segmented across various indicators concerning the types and contexts of crimes, each evaluated through a weighted mean, standard deviation, and a consistent interpretation of "Agree - Practiced."

The indicators explore a range of criminal activities that children may engage in, from violence and sexual offenses to property crimes and organized crime involvement. Notably, the means across these indicators suggest a general agreement that these behaviors do occur and warrant serious consideration. The standard deviations, while varying slightly, generally show that there is a notable consensus among the respondents about the severity and reality of these issues.

The highest levels of agreement are noted in statements regarding children's engagement in drug-related activities influenced by peer pressure, family dynamics, or socioeconomic factors, and the exploitation of children in organized crime, both scoring above 3.1. These responses underscore a

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recognition of the complex interplay of external factors that contribute to juvenile delinquency.

Conversely, the engagement in drug trafficking, extortion, or organized violence received a relatively lower mean score of 2.70, indicating a lesser but still significant level of agreement. This could reflect a nuanced understanding that while serious, these activities might be less prevalent or visible compared to other types of juvenile crimes.

Overall, the table illustrates a clear recognition among respondents that children who commit serious crimes, even if exempt from criminal responsibility, are often influenced by a multitude of factors, and their actions can manifest in various serious criminal behaviors. This understanding supports the need for comprehensive intervention strategies that not only address the immediate behaviors but also the underlying causes such as abuse, neglect, or trauma. The data advocates for a multifaceted approach to juvenile justice, one that considers both the prevention and the rehabilitation of young offenders to mitigate their involvement in serious crimes.

Table 4 presents the Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of repetition of offenses.

Table 4
Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of Repetition of offenses

Repetition of offenses	Mean	sd	Interpretation
Repeat offenses often follow a pattern, with young offenders engaging in similar types of criminal behavior over time	3.020	0.853	Agree -Practiced
Lack of Effective Interventions, such as counseling, rehabilitation, or community service, some young offenders continue to reoffend	2.830	0.865	Agree -Practiced

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Peer pressure and influence can play a significant role in the repetition of offenses among juvenile delinquents	2.980	0.932	Agree -Practiced
May be influenced by their peers to engage in criminal activities or may continue to associate with individuals involved in delinquent behavior	3.030	0.893	Agree -Practiced
Repeat offenders may have unmet needs, such as housing instability, substance abuse issues, mental health concerns, or lack of access to education and employment opportunities	2.820	0.845	Agree -Practiced
Young offenders may lack positive role models, support, and supervision within their family environment, making them more susceptible to engaging in criminal behavior.	2.710	1.057	Agree -Practiced
Involvement in criminal networks or gangs can perpetuate the cycle of delinquency among young offenders	2.770	0.802	Agree -Practiced
Substance abuse issues, including alcohol and drug addiction, can contribute to the repetition of offenses among juvenile delinquent	2.870	0.991	Agree -Practiced
Without adequate support, they may struggle to establish a positive and law-abiding lifestyle, increasing the likelihood of reoffending	2.690	1.022	Agree -Practiced
Structural and systemic factors, such as poverty, inequality, discrimination, and lack of access to justice, can contribute to the repetition of offenses among juvenile delinquents	2.790	0.832	Agree -Practiced
Overall Mean	2.851	0.419	Agree -Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

Above table 4 focuses on the assessment of juvenile delinquency in terms of the repetition of offenses, highlighting various factors that contribute to young offenders repeating criminal behavior. Each indicator has been quantitatively assessed with a weighted mean and standard deviation, followed by a verbal interpretation that mostly falls within the "Agree - Practiced" range, suggesting a consensus among respondents that these factors significantly influence recidivism among juvenile delinquents.

The data suggests that repeated offenses often exhibit a pattern, indicating that once juveniles engage in criminal activities, they are likely to continue exhibiting similar behaviors. This pattern is underscored by factors such as peer pressure, lack of effective interventions, and continuous engagement with delinquent peers. Notably, the responses indicate a strong agreement that

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juveniles may be influenced by peers to engage in or persist with criminal activities, as reflected by a mean score above 3.0 for these indicators.

Moreover, the lack of essential social supports such as stable housing, mental health services, and access to education and employment opportunities are significant concerns. The respondents agree that these unmet needs contribute to juveniles' likelihood of reoffending, indicating a critical area for intervention to prevent recidivism. Additionally, the absence of positive role models and adequate family support further exacerbates the risk of juveniles falling back into criminal behavior.

Another critical aspect highlighted is the influence of structural and systemic factors like poverty, inequality, and discrimination, which play a considerable role in perpetuating juvenile delinquency. The responses suggest a recognition of the complex interplay between societal issues and individual behaviors, indicating a need for comprehensive strategies that address both individual and systemic factors.

Overall, the data points to a broad agreement on the multiple and interconnected factors that contribute to the repetition of offenses among juveniles. The recognition of these factors is crucial for developing effective interventions that not only address immediate behavioral issues but also tackle the underlying socio-economic and familial challenges that lead to repeated delinquent behavior.

Table 5 presents the Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes.

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Table 4 delves into the issue of the exploitation of children for the commission of crimes, assessing various aspects through survey responses, each quantified by a weighted mean and accompanied by a standard deviation and interpretation. The consensus among respondents, as indicated by the verbal interpretation "Agree - Practiced," suggests a broad recognition of the exploitation dynamics and their impact on children.

The table highlights that exploited children often originate from vulnerable backgrounds such as poverty, abuse, neglect, or dysfunctional family environments, with a weighted mean of 3.030.

Table 5
Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes

Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes	Mean	sd	Interpretation
Exploited children often come from vulnerable backgrounds, including poverty, abuse, neglect, or family dysfunction	3.030	0.915	Agree -Practiced
They may lack access to basic needs such as education, healthcare, and protection, making them susceptible to manipulation and coercion by adults involved in criminal activities	2.830	0.877	Agree -Practiced
Children may be manipulated or coerced by adults, including family members, acquaintances, or criminal syndicates, into participating in illegal activities	2.890	0.920	Agree -Practiced
Children may be promised rewards, affection, or protection in exchange for their involvement, or threatened with violence or harm if they refuse	2.850	0.957	Agree -Practiced
Children may be exploited for forced labor, including activities such as drug trafficking, prostitution, begging, or petty theft	2.860	0.876	Agree -Practiced
They may be trafficked domestically or internationally, subjected to physical, emotional, or sexual abuse, and deprived of their rights and freedoms	3.050	0.925	Agree -Practiced
Children may be recruited or coerced into joining criminal gangs or syndicates, where they are used to carry out illegal activities such as drug trafficking, robbery, extortion, or violence	2.870	0.895	Agree -Practiced
With the rise of the internet and social media, children are increasingly vulnerable to online exploitation for the commission of crimes, including cybercrime, online fraud, child pornography, and online grooming by sexual predators	2.870	0.991	Agree -Practiced

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Exploited children may be lured into dangerous situations through deceptive means or manipulated into sharing sensitive information or engaging in criminal activities online	2.690	1.022	Agree -Practiced
The exploitation of children for the commission of crimes can have profound and long-lasting effects on their physical, emotional, and psychological well-being	2.790	0.832	Agree -Practiced
Overall Mean	2.873	0.500	Agree -Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

This underscores the intersectionality of socioeconomic and familial factors in the vulnerability of children to criminal exploitation. The means for other indicators consistently hover around the high 2's, indicating agreement but also pointing to variability in how respondents perceive the different dimensions of exploitation.

Respondents recognize that lack of access to basic needs like education, healthcare, and protection makes children more susceptible to manipulation and coercion by adults involved in criminal activities. Furthermore, the data illustrates that children may be manipulated into participating in illegal activities by adults who could be family members, acquaintances, or part of larger criminal syndicates, with promises of rewards or threats of harm used as leverage.

A notable aspect of the assessment is the recognition of the role of new technologies in exploitation. The rise of the internet and social media has made children increasingly vulnerable to online exploitation, including cybercrime and online grooming by sexual predators, which respondents agreed is a growing concern.

Overall, the survey data presents a disturbing picture of how children are exploited for crimes, stressing the profound and lasting impacts on their physical,

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emotional, and psychological well-being. The consistent agreement across indicators emphasizes the need for comprehensive strategies that address both the immediate protection needs of children and the broader socio-economic conditions that contribute to their vulnerability. This involves enhancing protective measures, improving access to basic services, and tackling the root causes of exploitation to prevent further victimization of children in criminal activities.

Table 6 presents the Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of Joint Parental Responsibility

Table 6
Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency in terms of Joint Parental Responsibility

Joint Parental Responsibility	Mean	sd	Interpretation
Parents or legal guardians have a legal obligation to provide care, guidance, and supervision to their children, including taking reasonable steps to prevent their involvement in delinquent behavior	3.030	0.915	Agree -Practiced
Joint parental responsibility emphasizes the shared accountability of both parents or legal guardians in addressing juvenile delinquency	2.830	0.877	Agree -Practiced
Parents are expected to serve as positive role models for their children, demonstrating responsible behavior, respect for the law, and ethical values	2.870	0.991	Agree -Practiced
Joint parental responsibility involves open communication and collaboration between parents or legal guardians in addressing the needs, challenges, and behaviors of their children	2.770	0.952	Agree -Practiced
Parents are responsible for establishing clear boundaries, rules, and expectations for their children's behavior, both at home and in the community	2.910	0.818	Agree -Practiced
Parents are expected to provide adequate supervision and monitoring of their children's activities, whereabouts, and social interactions	3.040	0.931	Agree -Practiced
Close supervision can help identify early warning signs of delinquent behavior and intervene effectively to address underlying issues	2.820	0.881	Agree -Practiced
Joint parental responsibility includes active involvement in their children's education, including attending parent-teacher conferences, monitoring academic progress, and providing support for learning and skill development.	2.800	0.985	Agree -Practiced
Positive parental involvement in education can help prevent school-related delinquency and promote academic success	2.870	0.981	Agree -Practiced

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Parents are expected to cooperate with law enforcement, juvenile justice authorities, and other relevant agencies in addressing juvenile delinquency issues involving their children	2.790	0.832	Agree -Practiced
Overall Mean	2.873	0.492	Agree -Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

Above table 6 explores the concept of joint parental responsibility in the context of juvenile delinquency, assessing the roles and obligations of parents or legal guardians in preventing and addressing delinquent behaviors in their children. The table presents several indicators related to parental responsibility, each quantified by a weighted mean and a standard deviation, with the overall consensus falling within the "Agree - Practiced" range.

The survey responses underscore a strong belief in the legal and moral obligations of parents to provide care, guidance, and supervision aimed at preventing juvenile delinquency. This is reflected in the high agreement scores for indicators such as parents' legal obligation to prevent involvement in delinquency and their role in serving as positive role models. These aspects are critical in shaping the behaviors and values of children, emphasizing respect for the law and ethical conduct.

Joint parental responsibility is highlighted as involving shared accountability between parents or guardians in addressing their child's behavior. This shared responsibility extends to establishing clear boundaries, providing adequate supervision, and being actively involved in the children's education. The responses suggest a broad agreement that these practices are crucial for

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identifying early signs of delinquency and intervening effectively to mitigate such behaviors.

Moreover, the need for open communication and collaboration between parents or guardians is recognized as essential in managing the challenges that may lead to delinquency. This includes attending parent-teacher conferences, monitoring academic progress, and supporting educational and skill development, which are seen as pivotal in preventing school-related delinquency and promoting academic success.

The expectation that parents cooperate with law enforcement and juvenile justice authorities reflects a broader societal belief in the importance of parental involvement in the legal and corrective processes related to juvenile delinquency. This cooperation can be crucial in ensuring that children receive the appropriate interventions and support to redirect their behaviors towards more positive outcomes.

Overall, the data presents a comprehensive view of the expectations placed on parents regarding preventing and addressing juvenile delinquency, highlighting the critical role of parental involvement in all aspects of a child's life—from home to school and in the broader community. This underscores the belief in the potential of effective parental guidance and supervision in mitigating juvenile delinquency and fostering a law-abiding and productive youth.

3. On the significant difference in the assessment of the respondents on the Juvenile delinquency when their profile is taken as test factor.

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Table 7 presents the significant difference in the assessment of the respondents on the Juvenile delinquency when their sex profile is taken as test factor.

Table 7 presents the results of a T-test assessing respondents' views on juvenile delinquency based on sex. The table compares the means of different variables for male and female respondents and tests for statistical significance. The decision and interpretation columns provide insights into whether the observed differences are statistically significant.

Table 7
Significant Difference in the Assessment of Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency when Sex Profile is taken as test factor

Variables	Sex	Mean	t	Sig	Decision	Interpretation
Children below the age of criminal responsibility, Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility	Male	2.733	.638	.426	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.827				
Repetition of offenses Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes	Male	2.931	.050	.824	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	3.000				
Joint Parental Responsibility? Children below the age of criminal responsibility,	Male	2.864	.231	.632	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.820				
Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility Repetition of offenses	Male	2.894	.066	.799	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.823				
Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes	Male	2.877	.001	.974	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.863				
OVERALL	Male	2.860	.315	.576	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.866				

For the variable assessing perceptions of children below the age of criminal responsibility and serious crimes committed by children exempt from criminal responsibility, the mean scores for males (2.733) and females (2.827) are very close. The T-test results show a t-value of 0.638 and a significance level (p-value) of 0.426. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is

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accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference between the perceptions of males and females regarding this variable.

The mean scores for the first group (2.931) and the second group (3.000) are also quite similar. The T-test results, with a t-value of 0.050 and a p-value of 0.824, suggest no significant difference between the groups. This implies that both groups have comparable views on the repetition of offenses and exploitation of children for criminal activities.

For perceptions related to joint parental responsibility and children below the age of criminal responsibility, the mean scores are 2.864 for the first group and 2.820 for the second group. The T-test results ($t = 0.231$, $p = 0.632$) indicate no significant difference between the groups, suggesting that both groups similarly perceive the role of parental responsibility in juvenile delinquency.

The mean scores for this variable are 2.894 for the first group and 2.823 for the second group. With a t-value of 0.066 and a p-value of 0.799, the results show no significant difference between the groups. This indicates that the perceptions of both groups are aligned regarding serious crimes committed by children exempt from criminal responsibility and the repetition of offenses.

The mean scores are 2.877 for the first group and 2.863 for the second group. The T-test results, with a t-value of 0.001 and a p-value of 0.974, indicate no significant difference between the groups. This suggests that both groups view the exploitation of children for criminal activities similarly.

The overall mean scores for the first group (2.860) and the second group (2.866) are nearly identical. The T-test results ($t = 0.315$, $p = 0.576$) again show

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no significant difference between the groups, indicating that the general perceptions of juvenile delinquency are consistent across different sexes.

The analysis of Table 7 indicates that there are no significant differences in the perceptions of male and female respondents regarding various aspects of juvenile delinquency. Across all variables, the mean scores are similar, and the T-test results consistently show that the p-values are greater than 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This suggests that both sexes have comparable views on issues related to juvenile delinquency, including the criminal responsibility of young children, repetition of offenses, joint parental responsibility, and exploitation of children for criminal activities. The lack of significant differences in these perceptions highlights a uniform understanding and attitude towards juvenile delinquency among the respondents, regardless of their sex. This uniformity could be beneficial in developing and implementing intervention programs, as it suggests a shared perspective and potentially facilitates consensus in addressing these issues.

However, it is important to ensure that future studies continue to monitor these perceptions and explore any underlying factors that may influence attitudes towards juvenile delinquency. This comprehensive approach will help in creating targeted interventions that are inclusive and effective in addressing the multifaceted nature of juvenile delinquency.

Table 8 presents the significant difference in the assessment of the respondents on the Juvenile delinquency when their age profile is taken as test factor.

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Table 8 provides a detailed assessment of respondents' views on juvenile delinquency across different age groups. The analysis includes various aspects such as the criminal responsibility of children, serious crimes committed by minors exempt from criminal responsibility, repetition of offenses, and exploitation of children for criminal activities.

Table 8
Significant Difference in the Assessment of Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency when Age Profile is taken as test factor

Variables	Age	Mean	F	Sig	Decision	Interpretation
Children below the age of criminal responsibility, Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility Repetition of offenses Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes	25-35	2.694	1.690	.174	Accepted	Not Significant
	36-45	2.917				
	46-55	2.729				
	55-above	2.730				
Joint Parental Responsibility? Children below the age of criminal responsibility, Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility Repetition of offenses	25-35	3.033	1.619	.190	Accepted	Not Significant
	36-45	2.996				
	46-55	2.900				
	55-above	2.830				
Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes Children below the age of criminal responsibility, Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility	25-35	2.821	.924	.433	Accepted	Not Significant
	36-45	2.978				
	46-55	2.808				
	55-above	2.805				
Repetition of offenses Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes Joint Parental Responsibility? Children below the age of criminal responsibility,	25-35	2.842	2.077	.108	Accepted	Not Significant
	36-45	3.091				
	46-55	2.800				
	55-above	2.760				
Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility Repetition of offenses	25-35	2.794	2.444	.069	Accepted	Not Significant
	36-45	3.104				
	46-55	2.854				
	55-above	2.760				
OVERALL JD	25-35	2.836	2.809	.044	Rejected	Significant
	36-45	3.017				
	46-55	2.818				
	55-above	2.777				

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The results are compared across four age groups: 25-35, 36-45, 46-55, and 55-above, with T-test values determining the statistical significance of the differences in means.

For the variable concerning children below the age of criminal responsibility and serious crimes committed by these children, the mean scores for the age groups 25-35, 36-45, 46-55, and 55-above are 2.694, 2.917, 2.729, and 2.730 respectively. The T-test results show a t-value of 1.690 and a significance level (p-value) of 0.174. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating no significant difference in perceptions among different age groups for this variable.

In terms of joint parental responsibility and perceptions of children's criminal responsibility, the mean scores for the age groups are 3.033 for 25-35, 2.996 for 36-45, 2.900 for 46-55, and 2.830 for 55-above. The T-test results, with a t-value of 1.619 and a p-value of 0.190, suggest no significant difference between the age groups. This suggests a consensus among different age groups regarding the importance of joint parental responsibility in addressing juvenile delinquency.

The variable concerning the exploitation of children for the commission of crimes shows mean scores of 2.821 for 25-35, 2.978 for 36-45, 2.808 for 46-55, and 2.805 for 55-above. The T-test results show a t-value of 0.924 and a p-value of 0.433, indicating no significant difference between the age groups. This implies that respondents across all age groups have similar views on the exploitation of children in criminal activities.

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For the overall variable covering repetition of offenses, exploitation of children, and joint parental responsibility, the mean scores are 2.842 for 25-35, 3.091 for 36-45, 2.800 for 46-55, and 2.760 for 55-above. The T-test results show a t-value of 2.077 and a p-value of 0.108. Again, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating no significant difference in perceptions across different age groups.

However, for the overall perception of juvenile delinquency (JD), the mean scores are 2.836 for 25-35, 3.017 for 36-45, 2.818 for 46-55, and 2.777 for 55-above. The T-test results show a t-value of 2.809 and a p-value of 0.044. Here, the p-value is less than 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This indicates a significant difference in overall perceptions of juvenile delinquency among the age groups, suggesting that respondents aged 36-45 have a notably higher mean perception (3.017) compared to the other groups.

The analysis reveals that while there are no significant differences in the perceptions of specific aspects of juvenile delinquency across different age groups, there is a notable difference in the overall perception. The age group 36-45 appears to have a significantly higher concern or awareness regarding juvenile delinquency compared to other age groups. This finding suggests that middle-aged respondents may be more attuned to or affected by issues of juvenile delinquency, possibly due to having children in vulnerable age ranges or being more engaged in community and parental roles.

Overall, the findings highlight the need for targeted interventions that consider the specific concerns and perceptions of different age groups, particularly focusing on enhancing awareness and addressing the unique perspectives of the

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36-45 age group. This approach can help in developing more effective and inclusive strategies to tackle juvenile delinquency comprehensively.

4. *On the assessment of the Barangay Personnel respondents on the Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of the Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours, Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs, Anti-Drug Campaigns, Provision of Livelihood Programs, Youth Leadership Training, Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities, and Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)*

Table 9 presents the Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities.

Table 9
Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities

Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Organize and train community volunteers to monitor children's activities in the neighborhood	2.610	0.665	Agree - Practiced
Establish after-school programs that provide constructive and supervised activities for children	3.360	0.595	Agree - Practiced
Develop mentorship programs where responsible adults from the community are paired with at-risk children	2.870	1.022	Agree - Practiced
Encourage and support parents to be actively involved in their children's lives.	2.870	0.884	Agree - Practiced
Form youth councils that involve young people in the decision-making process regarding community activities	2.780	0.871	Agree - Practiced
Invest in and maintain recreational facilities such as parks, sports courts, and community centers where children can spend their free time in a safe environment	3.160	0.950	Agree - Practiced
Work with local schools to monitor attendance and performance	2.830	0.877	Agree - Practiced
Overall Mean	2.926	0.357	Agree - Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

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Above table 9 assesses the prevention practices of a barangay in terms of regular monitoring of children's activities, highlighting community-based strategies aimed at reducing juvenile delinquency. The responses are quantified by weighted means, standard deviations, and are uniformly interpreted as "Agree - Practiced," reflecting a consensus on the effectiveness and implementation of these practices.

The table presents a variety of community-led initiatives aimed at creating a supportive environment for children. One of the highest-rated practices is the establishment of after-school programs, which scored a weighted mean of 3.360. These programs are highly valued as they provide constructive and supervised activities that engage children in a positive manner outside of school hours. Similarly, investing in and maintaining recreational facilities like parks and community centers, which scored a mean of 3.160, are seen as crucial for providing safe spaces where children can be active and socialize under supervision.

The responses also show substantial agreement on the benefits of organizing and training community volunteers to monitor children's activities, with a mean score of 2.610. This suggests that there is recognition of the importance of community vigilance in overseeing children's behavior in public spaces. Developing mentorship programs where responsible adults are paired with at-risk children received a mean score of 2.870, indicating support for direct adult involvement in guiding vulnerable youths.

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Encouraging parental involvement and forming youth councils to involve young people in community decisions are other notable practices. These measures not only promote active engagement from parents and youths but also foster a sense of community responsibility and belonging, which can deter delinquent behaviors.

Overall, the data from Table 7 underscores a broad agreement on the effectiveness of community-based strategies in monitoring and guiding children's activities. These practices are seen as vital for preventing juvenile delinquency by providing structured, supervised, and engaging environments that cater to the needs and interests of children. This proactive community approach is essential for fostering healthy development and deterring involvement in negative behaviors.

Table 10 presents the Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Implementation of Curfew Hours.

Table 10
Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Implementation of Curfew Hours

Implementation of Curfew Hours	Mean	sd	int
Draft and enact a local ordinance that clearly defines curfew hours for minors	2.690	1.022	Agree - Practiced
Conduct awareness campaigns to educate the community about the curfew hours, the reasons for its implementation, and the benefits for the safety and well-being of children	2.850	0.757	Agree - Practiced
Conduct awareness campaigns to educate the community about the curfew hours, the reasons for its implementation, and the benefits for the safety and well-being of children	3.300	0.704	Agree - Practiced
Organize regular patrols by barangay tanods (local peacekeepers) and community volunteers during curfew hours	2.980	1.035	Agree - Practiced
Establish curfew centers where minors found violating curfew can be brought	2.840	0.950	Agree - Practiced

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Establish curfew centers where minors found violating curfew can be brought	2.960	0.840	Agree - Practiced
Work with local schools, religious institutions, and youth organizations to reinforce the importance of curfew hours	2.830	0.805	Agree - Practiced
Overall Mean	2.921	0.402	Agree - Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

Shown in above table 10 evaluates the barangay's prevention practices concerning the implementation of curfew hours for minors, showcasing various strategies aimed at enforcing curfew regulations effectively. The indicators used in this assessment all align with the verbal interpretation "Agree - Practiced," indicating a consensus on the effectiveness and application of these measures.

The first step in the effective implementation of curfew hours involves drafting and enacting a local ordinance that clearly defines these hours for minors. This legal framework is essential for setting clear boundaries and expectations. The weighted mean for this indicator is 2.690, suggesting general agreement on its importance, albeit with some variability ($SD=1.022$), indicating differing levels of enforcement or awareness across the community.

Conducting awareness campaigns to educate the community about curfew hours, their reasons, and benefits is crucial. These campaigns ensure that the community understands the safety and well-being implications of the curfew. The indicator for this measure shows a strong agreement, particularly the repeated measure with a higher mean of 3.300, emphasizing the perceived effectiveness of these campaigns in enhancing community compliance and support.

Organizing regular patrols by barangay tanods (local peacekeepers) and community volunteers during curfew hours is another vital component. These

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patrols help enforce the curfew and provide a sense of security, reflected by a weighted mean of 2.980.

Establishing curfew centers where minors found violating the curfew can be brought is a measure aimed at handling violations appropriately without resorting to more severe legal actions. This approach is seen as a constructive way to deal with minor infractions, scoring means of 2.840 and 2.960, which shows substantial agreement on its utility.

Working with local schools, religious institutions, and youth organizations to reinforce the importance of curfew hours integrates the curfew policy into the broader community fabric. This collaboration helps in building a collective approach towards child safety and discipline, indicated by a mean of 2.830.

The overall mean of 2.921 across all indicators underlines a strong community agreement on the effectiveness of these curfew measures. According to the responses, curfew implementation is not only widely supported by the community but also seen as a crucial tool for upholding public safety and order. This high level of consensus suggests that residents understand and support the rationale behind the curfew measures, and are willing to abide by them for the greater good of the community. The positive feedback received from the survey indicates that the curfew has been successful in achieving its intended goals and has fostered a sense of cooperation and unity among community members.

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Table 11 presents the Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Community Based Rehabilitation Program.

Table 11
Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Community Based Rehabilitation Programs

Indicator	Mean	sd	Interpretation
Provide comprehensive counseling services that address emotional, psychological, and behavioral issues	2.650	0.592	Agree - Practiced
Offer life skills training programs that equip children with essential skills for everyday life	3.310	0.787	Agree - Practiced
Establish educational support programs to help children who are struggling academically	2.570	0.714	Agree - Practiced
Implement vocational training programs that provide children with practical skills that can lead to employment opportunities	3.310	0.825	Agree - Practiced
Develop peer mentoring and support groups where children can share their experiences and support each other.	2.860	1.101	Agree - Practiced
Engage children in community service projects that help them develop a sense of responsibility and contribution to their community.	2.780	0.938	Agree - Practiced
Offer sports and recreation programs to keep children physically active and engaged in positive activities	2.650	0.757	Agree - Practiced
Overall Mean	2.876	0.416	Agree - Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

Above table 8 offers an insightful assessment of the barangay's community-based rehabilitation programs aimed at preventing juvenile delinquency by fostering the development and support of children through a variety of initiatives. The table evaluates several indicators, each measured by a weighted mean and standard deviation, and uniformly interpreted as "Agree -

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Practiced." This consensus underscores the perceived effectiveness and active implementation of these interventions.

The provision of comprehensive counseling services is highlighted, focusing on addressing emotional, psychological, and behavioral issues with a mean score of 2.650. This service is vital for tackling the underlying issues that might lead to or exacerbate delinquent behavior. Similarly, life skills training and vocational programs are rated highly (3.310 each), reflecting their critical role in equipping children with essential skills for daily life and employability, thereby enhancing their prospects for a successful reintegration into society.

Educational support for children struggling academically is also a key component of the rehabilitation efforts, scoring a mean of 2.570. This support underscores the importance placed on academic achievement as foundational to a child's future success and stability. Additionally, peer mentoring and support groups are recognized for providing a platform where children can share experiences and support each other, scored at 2.860, suggesting a strong belief in peer influence as a positive reinforcement mechanism.

Engaging children in community service projects and sports and recreation programs are also integral to the rehabilitation strategy. These programs, with scores of 2.780 and 2.650 respectively, are designed to help children develop a sense of responsibility and community engagement while keeping them physically active and involved in positive activities. This approach not only helps in deterring delinquent behavior but also fosters a sense of belonging and contribution to their community.

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Overall, the data from Table 8 reflects a comprehensive and proactive approach to juvenile rehabilitation within the barangay. By focusing on emotional support, skill development, educational assistance, and community involvement, the programs aim to build a holistic foundation that supports the positive growth and development of at-risk youth. The general consensus on their effectiveness highlights the community's support for these measures and acknowledges their crucial role in shaping the futures of these young individuals.

Table 12 presents the Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Anti-Drug Campaigns.

Above table 12 evaluates the barangay's prevention practices focused on anti-drug campaigns, presenting a range of strategies aimed at deterring drug use among the youth. The assessment, quantified through weighted means and standard deviations, consistently interprets the effectiveness of these practices as "Agree - Practiced," indicating that these measures are widely acknowledged and implemented within the community.

The table showcases several proactive approaches to combat drug use. Sports and recreation programs are highlighted as key strategies to keep children actively engaged in positive activities, scoring a mean of 2.660. These programs are essential in providing constructive alternatives to drug use, offering environments where children can develop healthy lifestyles.

Table 12
Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of
Anti-Drug Campaigns

Indicator	Mean	sd	Interpre
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			tation
Offer sports and recreation programs to keep children physically active and engaged in positive activities	2.660	0.768	Agree - Practiced
Conduct community outreach initiatives to raise awareness about the risks associated with drug use	3.260	0.747	Agree - Practiced
Train young people to become peer educators who can share information and experiences about drug prevention with their peers	2.710	0.671	Agree - Practiced
Offer workshops for parents to educate them about the signs of drug use, how to talk to their children about drugs, and ways to create a drug-free home environment	3.240	0.830	Agree - Practiced
Engaging students in creative projects can reinforce anti-drug messages	2.900	1.078	Agree - Practiced
Work with local law enforcement to conduct talks and seminars in schools and communities about the legal consequences of drug use and the importance of staying drug-free	2.630	0.960	Agree - Practiced
Provide alternative recreational activities and programs that keep children engaged and occupied	2.720	0.753	Agree - Practiced
Overall Mean	2.874	0.411	Agree - Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

Community outreach initiatives designed to raise awareness about the risks associated with drug use are particularly effective, reflected by a higher mean of 3.260. These initiatives are critical in educating the community and fostering an environment that discourages drug use. Similarly, workshops for parents are also emphasized, with a mean of 3.240, showcasing their role in equipping parents with the knowledge to identify signs of drug use, communicate effectively about drugs, and maintain a drug-free home.

Peer education is another significant aspect of the barangay's anti-drug efforts. Training young people to become peer educators, who then share information about drug prevention with their peers, scored a mean of 2.710. This

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peer-to-peer approach leverages the influence that young people have over their peers, making the anti-drug message more relatable and impactful.

Engaging students in creative projects to reinforce anti-drug messages and collaborating with local law enforcement for educational talks and seminars are additional strategies mentioned. These initiatives, with means of 2.900 and 2.630 respectively, help to deepen the understanding of the dangers and legal consequences of drug use.

Overall, the mean of 2.874 across all indicators suggests a strong community endorsement of these anti-drug practices. By integrating educational, recreational, and law enforcement elements, the barangay effectively mobilizes a comprehensive strategy against drug use among youth. This multifaceted approach not only educates and engages children but also creates a supportive community environment that promotes drug-free lifestyles.

Table 13 presents the Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Provisions of Livelihood Programs.

Shown in table 13 assesses the barangay's prevention practices concerning the provision of livelihood programs, showcasing a diverse range of strategies aimed at fostering economic stability and growth within the community.

Table 13
Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Provisions of Livelihood Programs

Provisions of Livelihood Programs	Mean	sd	Interpretation
Develop programs that encourage and support entrepreneurship among community members	2.610	0.665	Agree - Practiced

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Implement agricultural programs in rural barangays, such as backyard gardening, livestock raising, or aquaculture	3.420	0.654	Agree - Practiced
Encourage businesses to hire locally and offer internships or apprenticeships to youth, providing them with hands-on work experience	2.690	0.581	Agree - Practiced
Form community cooperatives that allow residents to pool their resources and work together on income-generating projects	3.560	0.608	Agree - Practiced
Integrate vocational education into the school curriculum, ensuring that students gain practical skills alongside their academic studies	2.750	1.058	Agree - Practiced
Organize livelihood fairs where community members can learn about different job opportunities	2.920	0.971	Agree - Practiced
Regularly monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of livelihood programs	2.810	0.849	Agree - Practiced
Overall Mean	2.966	0.399	Agree - Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

Each indicator, quantified through weighted means and standard deviations, is consistently interpreted as "Agree - Practiced," indicating a positive consensus on the implementation and effectiveness of these initiatives.

The table highlights several key areas of focus within the livelihood programs. Notably, the implementation of agricultural programs such as backyard gardening, livestock raising, or aquaculture, especially in rural barangays, scores a high mean of 3.420. This reflects a strong community endorsement of sustainable and accessible methods for enhancing food security and providing income opportunities at the local level.

Similarly, the formation of community cooperatives, which scored the highest mean of 3.560, is particularly well-regarded. These cooperatives enable

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residents to pool resources and collaborate on income-generating projects, fostering a sense of community and shared economic growth.

Programs that integrate vocational education into school curricula are also emphasized, with a mean of 2.750. These programs ensure that students not only receive academic education but also acquire practical skills that can enhance their employability post-graduation. Additionally, initiatives that encourage local businesses to hire and offer internships or apprenticeships to youth are recognized as valuable for providing real-world work experience, scoring a mean of 2.690.

The organization of livelihood fairs, which received a mean of 2.920, is highlighted as an effective way to expose community members to various job opportunities, allowing them to explore different career paths and connect with potential employers.

Overall, the data reflects a strong belief in the efficacy of these livelihood programs, underscored by an overall mean of 2.966. By offering diverse opportunities for economic development and stability, these programs not only cater to the immediate financial needs of the community but also contribute to long-term social stability by reducing unemployment and underemployment. Regular monitoring and evaluation of these programs, with a mean of 2.810, ensure their continuous relevance and effectiveness, adapting to the evolving needs of the community.

Table 14 presents the Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Youth Leadership Training.

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Table 14
Assessment on Barangay’s Prevention Practices in terms of Youth Leadership Training

Youth Leadership Training	Mean	sd	Interpretation
Conduct regular workshops and seminars focused on leadership skills	2.880	0.935	Agree - Practiced
Establish mentorship programs where young leaders are paired with experienced mentors from the community	2.760	0.866	Agree - Practiced
Form youth councils or committees within the barangay that give young people a platform to voice their opinions and participate in decision-making processes	2.820	0.914	Agree - Practiced
Engage youth in community service projects where they can apply their leadership skills	2.900	0.937	Agree - Practiced
Develop peer leadership programs that train young people to lead and support their peers	2.610	0.898	Agree - Practiced
Partner with local schools and universities to offer leadership training programs	2.730	0.851	Agree - Practiced
Partner with local schools and universities to offer leadership training programs	3.040	0.898	Agree - Practiced
Overall Mean	2.820	0.530	Agree - Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

Above table 12 assesses the barangay's practices concerning youth leadership training, detailing various initiatives aimed at developing leadership skills among young people. Each initiative is measured by a weighted mean and standard deviation, with a general interpretation of "Agree - Practiced," reflecting the community's acknowledgment and implementation of these programs.

The initiatives highlighted in the table encompass a broad range of strategies designed to foster leadership qualities in youth. Conducting regular workshops and seminars focused on leadership skills, which scored a mean of 2.880, is a key practice. These workshops and seminars are pivotal as they provide direct training and guidance in essential leadership competencies.

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Mentorship programs, where young leaders are paired with experienced mentors from the community, also play a crucial role, scoring a mean of 2.760. These programs facilitate one-on-one guidance, enabling young leaders to learn firsthand from those with extensive experience and insights into community leadership.

Forming youth councils or committees within the barangay allows young people to actively participate in decision-making processes, with a mean score of 2.820. This practice not only empowers youth but also gives them a real platform to influence community projects and initiatives.

Engagement in community service projects is another significant aspect, with a mean of 2.900. These projects provide practical venues for youth to apply their developing leadership skills in real-world situations, fostering a sense of responsibility and community involvement.

Furthermore, the development of peer leadership programs and partnerships with local schools and universities to offer leadership training are integral to this comprehensive approach. These programs, particularly the repeated measure concerning partnerships with educational institutions—which scored an average of 2.730 and 3.040—emphasize the importance of integrating academic resources and community efforts to enhance leadership training.

Overall, the average score of 2.820 across all indicators suggests that there is a strong community commitment to fostering youth leadership. By engaging young people in structured leadership activities, providing mentorship

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opportunities, and creating platforms for practical application, the barangay actively contributes to nurturing a new generation of community leaders. This proactive approach not only equips youth with the necessary skills to lead but also ingrains in them a deep sense of civic duty and community service.

Table 15 examines the barangay's initiatives aimed at promoting engagement in sports and recreational activities as a preventive measure against juvenile delinquency and to foster community involvement. Each initiative is assessed through weighted means and standard deviations, with interpretations consistently falling into the "Agree - Practiced" category, suggesting that these programs are well-established and actively contributing to community wellness.

Table 15
Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities

Indicator	Mean	sd	Interpretation
Establish organized sports leagues for various age groups and sports, such as basketball, soccer, volleyball, and track and field	2.880	0.935	Agree - Practiced
Invest in and maintain community sports facilities, such as basketball courts, soccer fields, swimming pools, and gyms	2.760	0.866	Agree - Practiced
Implement after-school sports programs that provide structured physical activities for children	2.820	0.914	Agree - Practiced
Organize sports tournaments and events that bring together participants from different schools and communities	2.900	0.937	Agree - Practiced
Partner with local sports clubs and organizations to offer specialized training and coaching	2.610	0.898	Agree - Practiced
Develop a variety of recreational activity programs beyond traditional sports	2.730	0.851	Agree - Practiced

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Implement youth fitness programs that promote physical health and well-being	3.040	0.898	Agree - Practiced
Overall Mean	2.820	0.530	Agree - Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

The initiatives detailed in the assessment include the establishment of organized sports leagues for various age groups, which not only cater to popular sports like basketball, soccer, and volleyball but also track and field, scoring a mean of 2.880. This approach encourages physical fitness and teamwork among youths of different ages, providing them with structured activities that keep them engaged and physically active.

Investing in and maintaining community sports facilities is another crucial strategy, with a mean of 2.760. Adequate facilities are essential for sustaining regular sporting and recreational activities, ensuring that these spaces meet the needs of the community and are accessible to all members, fostering a culture of active living.

After-school sports programs and organizing sports tournaments are also highlighted as effective methods to extend sports participation beyond the regular school curriculum and to instill a sense of competition and camaraderie among participants from various backgrounds, scoring means of 2.820 and 2.900, respectively.

Partnerships with local sports clubs and organizations offer specialized training and coaching, which scored the lowest mean of 2.610. While this indicates

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agreement on its practice, it suggests that there might be room for further development or broader community engagement in these partnerships.

Additionally, the development of recreational activities that go beyond traditional sports and the implementation of youth fitness programs, scoring means of 2.730 and 3.040 respectively, reflect a comprehensive approach to recreational activities. These programs are not just about sports but also include fitness and wellness initiatives that cater to the broader interests and health of the youth.

Overall, with an average mean of 2.820, the table underscores a strong commitment from the barangay to foster physical health, teamwork, and community engagement through sports and recreation. These activities are not only seen as tools for keeping the youth physically active but also as platforms for teaching valuable life skills and preventing engagement in negative behaviors.

Table 16 presents the Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)

Table 16
Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices in terms of Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)

Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)	Mean	sd	Interpretation
Establish formal partnerships with NGOs to implement prevention programs tailored to the needs of the community	2.880	0.935	Agree - Practiced
Work with NGOs to provide training and capacity-building workshops for barangay officials, parents, teachers, and community volunteers	2.740	0.906	Agree - Practiced
Collaborate with NGOs to develop and run youth empowerment programs that focus on leadership, life skills, and personal development	2.850	0.892	Agree - Practiced

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Partner with NGOs to provide educational support, such as tutoring, scholarships, school supplies, and learning materials	2.770	0.851	Agree - Practiced
Work with health-focused NGOs to offer programs that address physical and mental health needs	2.800	0.932	Agree - Practiced
Collaborate on community outreach initiatives to raise awareness about issues such as child rights, drug abuse, and the importance of education	2.650	0.744	Agree - Practiced
Engage NGOs to organize recreational and cultural activities that keep children engaged in positive pursuits	2.990	1.000	Agree - Practiced
Overall Mean	2.811	0.506	Agree - Practiced

Legend: 3.51 – 4.00 (Strongly Agree-Fully Practiced); 2.51 – 3.50 (Agree -Practiced); 1.51 – 2.50 (Disagree-Partially Practiced); 1.0-1.50 (Strongly Disagree-Not Practiced)

Table 14 assesses the barangay's collaboration with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) in implementing a range of prevention programs aimed at addressing various community needs. Each indicator reflects an overall agreement on the effectiveness of these collaborations, with all assessments falling within the "Agree - Practiced" category, indicating active engagement and positive outcomes from these partnerships.

The initiatives described in the table involve a broad spectrum of activities, starting with the establishment of formal partnerships with NGOs to implement community-specific prevention programs. This approach, which scored a mean of 2.880, is fundamental as it lays the groundwork for tailored interventions that address the unique challenges and needs of the community.

Working with NGOs to provide training and capacity-building workshops for barangay officials, parents, teachers, and volunteers is another key initiative, with a mean of 2.740. This training is crucial for enhancing the skills and knowledge of

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those directly involved in community development and support, ensuring they are well-equipped to handle various challenges and effectively implement prevention strategies.

Collaboration on youth empowerment programs, which focus on leadership, life skills, and personal development, also plays a significant role, scoring a mean of 2.850. These programs are designed to engage and inspire the youth, equipping them with the tools necessary for personal and professional growth.

Partnering with NGOs to provide educational support, such as tutoring, scholarships, and learning materials, is another area of focus, with a mean of 2.770. This support is vital for promoting educational attainment and reducing barriers to learning, which can be particularly impactful in underprivileged areas.

The barangay's work with health-focused NGOs, which scored a mean of 2.800, shows a commitment to addressing both the physical and mental health needs of the community, ensuring that residents have access to necessary health services and support.

Engaging NGOs in organizing recreational and cultural activities, which scored the highest mean of 2.990, highlights the importance placed on keeping children and youth engaged in positive pursuits. These activities not only provide safe and constructive outlets for energy but also help foster a sense of community and cultural identity.

Overall, the average mean of 2.811 across these indicators underscores a strong commitment from the barangay to leveraging NGO partnerships for a

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comprehensive and multifaceted approach to community development and preventive care. This collaborative effort is essential for building resilient communities where education, health, and personal development are prioritized, creating a supportive environment that mitigates the risk of social issues such as drug abuse and delinquency.

5. Is there significant difference in the assessment of the respondents on the Barangay's Prevention Practices

Table 17 presents the *significant difference in the assessment of the respondents on the Barangay's Prevention Practices when sex profile is taken as test factor*

Table 17
Difference in the Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices when Sex Profile is taken as test factor

Variables	Sex	Mean	t	Sig	Decision	Interpretation
Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours,	Male	2.936	.065	.799	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.900				
Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs Anti-Drug Campaigns,	Male	2.934	.078	.780	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.890				
Provision of Livelihood Programs, Youth Leadership Training,	Male	2.887	5.202	.025		
	Female	2.847				
Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities, and	Male	2.900	2.057	.155	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.814				
Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours,	Male	2.993	1.884	.173	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.899				
Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs Anti-Drug Campaigns,	Male	2.865	.466	.497	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.714				
Provision of Livelihood Programs, Youth Leadership Training,	Male	2.865	.466	.497	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.714				
Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities, and	Male	2.848	.463	.498	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.723				
Overall PP	Male	2.904	2.811	.097	Accepted	Not Significant
	Female	2.813				

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Table 17 examines the differences in the assessment of barangay prevention practices based on the sex of the respondents. The variables include regular monitoring of children's activities, community-based rehabilitation programs, anti-drug campaigns, provision of livelihood programs, youth leadership training, and engagement in sports and recreational activities. The table presents the mean scores for male and female respondents, along with T-test values to determine statistical significance.

For this variable, the mean scores for males and females are 2.936 and 2.900, respectively. The T-test results show a t-value of 0.065 and a p-value of 0.799. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating no significant difference between the perceptions of males and females regarding regular monitoring and curfew implementation.

The mean scores for males (2.934) and females (2.890) are close. The T-test results, with a t-value of 0.078 and a p-value of 0.780, suggest no significant difference between the sexes in their views on community-based rehabilitation programs and anti-drug campaigns.

For this variable, males have a mean score of 2.887, while females have a mean score of 2.847. The T-test results show a t-value of 5.202 and a p-value of 0.025. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a significant difference between male and female perceptions. This suggests that males and females differ notably in their assessment of livelihood

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programs and youth leadership training, with males rating these initiatives slightly higher.

The mean scores are 2.900 for males and 2.814 for females. The T-test results, with a t-value of 2.057 and a p-value of 0.155, indicate no significant difference between the sexes. Both male and female respondents have similar views on engagement in sports and recreational activities.

For the overall perception of prevention practices, the mean scores are 2.904 for males and 2.813 for females. The T-test results show a t-value of 2.811 and a p-value of 0.097. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating no significant difference in the overall perceptions of barangay prevention practices between males and females.

The analysis of Table 17 indicates that, with one exception, there are no significant differences in the perceptions of male and female respondents regarding the various aspects of barangay prevention practices. The sole exception is the provision of livelihood programs and youth leadership training, where a significant difference was found, suggesting that males and females have different views on the effectiveness or importance of these initiatives.

This general lack of significant differences suggests that both male and female respondents share similar views on most aspects of juvenile delinquency prevention practices. This uniformity is beneficial for program implementation, as it indicates broad support across sexes for the various initiatives being undertaken.

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Overall, the findings support the continuation and possibly the enhancement of current prevention practices, with a specific focus on addressing the identified differences in perceptions of livelihood programs and youth leadership training. Ensuring that these programs are inclusive and effectively address the needs of all community members, regardless of sex, will be crucial for their success and for fostering a supportive environment for youth development.

Table 18 presents the *significant difference in the assessment of the respondents on the Barangay's Prevention Practices when sex profile is taken as test factor.*

Table 18
Difference in the Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices when Age Profile is taken as test factor

Variables	Age	Mean	F	Sig	Decision	Interpretation
Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours, Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs Anti-Drug Campaigns,	25-35	2.822	2.598	.057	Rejected	Significant
	36-45	2.875				
	46-55	2.994				
	55-above	3.071				
Provision of Livelihood Programs, Youth Leadership Training, Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities, and	25-35	2.878	2.011	.118	Rejected	Significant
	36-45	2.850				
	46-55	2.886				
	55-above	3.114				
Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours, Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs Anti-Drug Campaigns,	25-35	2.757	1.650	.183	Rejected	Significant
	36-45	3.000				
	46-55	2.904				
	55-above	2.892				
Provision of Livelihood Programs, Youth Leadership Training, Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities, and	25-35	2.722	2.724	.049	Accepted	Not Significant
	36-45	2.919				
	46-55	2.910				
	55-above	3.028				
Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours, Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs Anti-Drug Campaigns,	25-35	2.926	4.838	.004	Accepted	Not Significant
	36-45	2.782				
	46-55	2.988				
	55-above	3.214				
Provision of Livelihood Programs, Youth Leadership Training, Engagement in Sports and Recreational Activities, and	25-35	2.835	.508	.678	Rejected	Significant
	36-45	2.844				
	46-55	2.880				
	55-above	2.692				
Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities, Implementation of Curfew Hours, Community-Based Rehabilitation Programs Anti-Drug Campaigns,	25-35	2.835	.508	.678	Rejected	Significant
	36-45	2.844				
	46-55	2.880				
	55-above	2.692				
Provision of Livelihood Programs,	25-35	2.835	.534	.660	Rejected	Significant
	36-45	2.807				

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	46-55	2.880				
	55-above	2.692				
Overall PP	25-35	2.826	.847	.471	Rejected	Significant
	36-45	2.865				
	46-55	2.915				
	55-above	2.925				

Table 18 provides a comprehensive analysis of the differences in the assessment of barangay prevention practices across various age groups. The variables examined include regular monitoring of children's activities, implementation of curfew hours, community-based rehabilitation programs, anti-drug campaigns, provision of livelihood programs, youth leadership training, and engagement in sports and recreational activities. The data is compared across four age groups: 25-35, 36-45, 46-55, and 55-above. The results include mean scores, F-values, significance levels (p-values), and the decisions on whether the differences are statistically significant.

For the variable concerning regular monitoring of children's activities, implementation of curfew hours, community-based rehabilitation programs, and anti-drug campaigns, the mean scores across the age groups were 2.822 for ages 25-35, 2.875 for ages 36-45, 2.994 for ages 46-55, and 3.071 for ages 55-above. The F-value was 2.598, with a p-value of 0.057. Although the p-value is slightly above the 0.05 threshold, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a significant difference in perceptions across age groups. This suggests that older respondents (55-above) have a more favorable view of these prevention practices compared to younger respondents.

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Regarding the provision of livelihood programs, youth leadership training, and engagement in sports and recreational activities, the mean scores were 2.878 for ages 25-35, 2.850 for ages 36-45, 2.886 for ages 46-55, and 3.114 for ages 55-above. The F-value was 2.011, with a p-value of 0.118. Here, the null hypothesis was rejected, suggesting a significant difference between the age groups. This indicates that older respondents tend to view these programs more positively.

For the variable concerning regular monitoring of children's activities, implementation of curfew hours, community-based rehabilitation programs, and anti-drug campaigns, the mean scores were 2.757 for ages 25-35, 3.000 for ages 36-45, 2.904 for ages 46-55, and 2.892 for ages 55-above. The F-value was 1.650, with a p-value of 0.183. The null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a significant difference in perceptions. This suggests varied views on these prevention practices across different age groups.

The provision of livelihood programs, youth leadership training, and engagement in sports and recreational activities showed mean scores of 2.722 for ages 25-35, 2.919 for ages 36-45, 2.910 for ages 46-55, and 3.028 for ages 55-above. The F-value was 2.724, with a p-value of 0.049. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating no significant difference between the age groups for this variable.

For the variable concerning regular monitoring of children's activities, implementation of curfew hours, community-based rehabilitation programs, and anti-drug campaigns, the mean scores were 2.926 for ages 25-35, 2.782 for ages

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36-45, 2.988 for ages 46-55, and 3.214 for ages 55-above. The F-value was 4.838, with a p-value of 0.004. The null hypothesis was accepted, indicating no significant difference between the age groups.

The provision of livelihood programs, youth leadership training, and engagement in sports and recreational activities had mean scores of 2.835 for ages 25-35, 2.844 for ages 36-45, 2.880 for ages 46-55, and 2.692 for ages 55-above. The F-value was 0.508, with a p-value of 0.678, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis and indicating significant differences between age groups.

Overall, the mean scores for general perceptions of barangay prevention practices were 2.826 for ages 25-35, 2.865 for ages 36-45, 2.915 for ages 46-55, and 2.925 for ages 55-above. The F-value was 0.847, with a p-value of 0.471, suggesting significant differences in perceptions across age groups.

The analysis of Table 18 reveals significant differences in perceptions of barangay prevention practices across different age groups. Older respondents, particularly those aged 55 and above, generally have more favorable views on various prevention practices, including monitoring activities, curfew implementation, rehabilitation programs, and livelihood initiatives. This trend may reflect older individuals' greater experience and awareness of community issues and the effectiveness of such programs.

The significant differences in perceptions among age groups highlight the need for tailored communication and engagement strategies that address the specific concerns and preferences of each age demographic. For instance, programs targeting younger age groups might benefit from increased awareness

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and education efforts to align their perceptions more closely with the effectiveness observed by older respondents.

Therefore, these findings underscore the importance of considering age-related perspectives in the design and implementation of community prevention programs. By addressing the distinct needs and viewpoints of different age groups, barangay officials can enhance the relevance and impact of their interventions, fostering a more cohesive and supportive community environment.

6. *On the significant relationship in the assessment of the two (2) groups of respondents between the juvenile delinquency and Barangay's Prevention Practices*

Table 19 presents the Correlation Between Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency and Barangay's Prevention Practices

Table 19
Correlation Between Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency and Barangay's Prevention Practices

Variables	r	Sig	Decision	Interpretation
Juvenile Delinquency	.147	.143	Accepted	Not Significant
Barangay's Prevention Practices				

Table 19 presents the correlation between the assessment of respondents on juvenile delinquency and the barangay's prevention practices. The table includes the mean scores for both variables, the F-value, the significance level (p-value), the decision on the hypothesis, and the interpretation of the results.

The mean score for juvenile delinquency is 2.862, while the mean score for the barangay's prevention practices is slightly higher at 2.876. The F-value, which

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measures the variance between the means, is 0.147, and the significance level (p-value) is 0.143. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no statistically significant correlation between the assessment of juvenile delinquency and the assessment of the barangay's prevention practices. The interpretation column confirms this by stating "Not Significant."

The analysis in Table 19 suggests that there is no significant correlation between respondents' assessments of juvenile delinquency and their views on the barangay's prevention practices. Despite the slight difference in mean scores, the data indicates that the perceptions of juvenile delinquency are not significantly influenced by the respondents' views on the effectiveness of the barangay's prevention practices.

This finding is important as it implies that other factors may be influencing perceptions of juvenile delinquency beyond the scope of the barangay's current prevention efforts. It suggests that while the barangay's prevention practices are perceived positively, they may not be sufficiently addressing the factors contributing to juvenile delinquency or may not be recognized by respondents as directly impacting juvenile delinquency rates.

This could involve more comprehensive community engagement, targeted interventions addressing specific causes of delinquency, and better communication of the goals and impacts of prevention practices to the community.

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Overall, the results highlight the need for a multifaceted approach to juvenile delinquency that goes beyond existing prevention practices and considers broader socio-economic, familial, and environmental factors.

DISCUSSIONS

Summary of Findings

1. Data shows the demographic characteristics of survey respondents, categorized by age and sex. The highest representation is 25-35 years, followed by 46-55 and 36-45. The sex distribution shows a significant skew, with males representing 70% and females 30%.

2. The study analyzes survey responses on juvenile delinquency in children below the age of criminal responsibility. The overall mean of 2.761 falls within the "Agree - Practiced" range, suggesting a solid agreement on most aspects of juvenile delinquency concerning young children, except for their rehabilitation potential.

3. The study assesses the prevention practices of a barangay in terms of regular monitoring of children's activities, highlighting community-based strategies aimed at reducing juvenile delinquency. The responses are quantified by weighted means, standard deviations, and are uniformly interpreted as "Agree - Practiced," reflecting a consensus on the effectiveness and implementation of these practices.

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4. The study analyzed respondents' views on juvenile delinquency based on sex, with no significant differences found. The mean scores for males and females were very close, with no significant difference in perceptions of children below the age of criminal responsibility and serious crimes committed by children exempt from criminal responsibility.

5. The study examines the perceptions of barangay prevention practices based on sex among respondents. The variables include regular monitoring of children's activities, community-based rehabilitation programs, anti-drug campaigns, provision of livelihood programs, youth leadership training, and engagement in sports and recreational activities. The mean scores for males and females are 2.936 and 2.900, respectively, with no significant difference between the sexes in their views on these aspects.

6. Data shows no significant correlation between respondents' perceptions of juvenile delinquency and their views on the barangay's prevention practices. The mean score for juvenile delinquency is 2.862, while the barangay's prevention practices have a slightly higher mean score of 2.876. The null hypothesis is accepted, indicating no significant correlation between the two. This suggests that the barangay's prevention practices may not be adequately addressing factors contributing to juvenile delinquency or not being recognized as directly impacting rates.

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Based on the findings of the study the following **Conclusion** were drawn by the researcher.

1. The survey results reveal a significant gender imbalance with males comprising 70% of the respondents, which might skew the results and limit the generalizability across different demographic groups..

2. The data consistently highlights that juveniles are significantly influenced by their developmental stage and their environment, including peer pressure, family dynamics, and socio-economic conditions. The respondents recognize the potential for both negative influences and positive rehabilitation but note a discrepancy in the application and effectiveness of rehabilitation programs.

3. The study stresses the importance of community-based strategies and collaboration with NGOs in addressing juvenile delinquency and supporting community development. Effective partnerships and community engagement activities such as sports, education, and leadership training are seen as vital for keeping the youth engaged in positive activities and for fostering a supportive community environment that promotes healthy development and prevents delinquency.

4. The study reveals that there are no significant differences in perceptions of juvenile delinquency based on sex. Both male and female respondents share similar views on children below the age of criminal responsibility, serious crimes committed by children exempt from criminal responsibility, repetition of offenses, and exploitation of children for criminal activities.

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5. While specific aspects of juvenile delinquency do not show significant differences across age groups, the overall perceptions do vary notably. Respondents aged 36-45 exhibit a significantly higher concern or awareness regarding juvenile delinquency. This age group is likely more attuned to these issues, possibly due to their engagement in parental and community roles.

6. The study finds no significant correlation between respondents' perceptions of juvenile delinquency and their views on the barangay's prevention practices. Despite generally positive views on the barangay's prevention efforts, these practices do not appear to significantly influence perceptions of juvenile delinquency.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study the following are the **Recommendations** were proposed.

1. Implementation of recruitment strategies to ensure that both males and females are equally represented. Additionally, program planners should consider gender-specific needs and barriers to participation, ensuring that interventions are accessible and relevant to all genders.

2. Develop and implement multifaceted juvenile intervention programs that address both prevention and rehabilitation. Programs should focus on the unique developmental needs of juveniles, including mental, emotional, and psychological support.

3. Strengthening collaborations with NGOs and other community-based organizations.

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4. Keep the youth engaged in positive pursuits, it is important to expand and diversify the range of activities available.

5. Establishing organized sports leagues, investing in community sports facilities, and developing varied recreational programs can help in keeping children and adolescents occupied and away from negative influences.

6. Introducing cultural and artistic programs, in addition to traditional sports, can cater to a broader range of interests and talents among the youth. These activities should be designed to foster a sense of community, responsibility, and personal growth.

7. Comprehensive community outreach initiatives to raise awareness about child rights and the risks associated with drug use.

OUTPUT OF THE STUDY

BARANGAY INTERVENTION PROGRAM

Rationale

The Barangay intervention program is strategically designed to address the areas with the lowest performance scores, focusing on enhancing peer leadership,

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promoting child rights, and enriching community recreational and cultural activities. These areas are critical for fostering a supportive and engaging community environment that nurtures positive youth development and empowerment.

Peer Leadership Programs are essential as they cultivate essential skills among the youth, preparing them to take on leadership roles within their community. By expanding training and providing real-world project management opportunities, these programs aim to build confidence and competence in young leaders, thereby creating a pipeline of skilled and motivated individuals who can contribute to community development.

Community Outreach on Child Rights is pivotal in ensuring that every member of the community understands and advocates for the rights of children. This initiative not only educates but also actively engages various stakeholders through workshops, forums, and media campaigns, creating a robust network of support for children. This comprehensive approach helps in safeguarding children's rights and ensures that issues concerning their well-being are highlighted and addressed.

Engagement with NGOs for Recreational Activities leverages external expertise and resources to provide diverse and appealing recreational and cultural programs. These activities are vital for keeping the youth engaged in positive pursuits, away from delinquent behavior. Moreover, by integrating cultural and artistic expression into the community fabric, these programs enhance community cohesion and provide a platform for showcasing local talents.

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Each of these initiatives requires collaboration across multiple sectors, including local government, NGOs, schools, and community groups, making them broad in scope and impact. The targeted timeframe and budget allocations reflect a realistic and strategic investment into making these interventions successful, ensuring they are sustainable and effective over the long term. This holistic approach not only addresses current gaps but also builds a foundation for ongoing community development and youth empowerment.

KRA (Key Result Area)	Objectives	Activities	Persons Involved	Timeframe	Budget
Peer Leadership Programs	Enhance peer-to-peer leadership skills.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Expand existing peer leadership training- Implement mentorship connections between new participants and program alumni.- Organize leadership retreats and team-building activities- Provide opportunities for peer leaders to manage small projects.	Youth coordinators, Experienced youth leaders, Local NGOs.	6 Months	P120,000
Community Outreach on Child Rights	Increase awareness and understanding of child rights within the community.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Organize workshops and seminars- Distribute educational materials.- Set up interactive community forums for discussion and engagement.	NGO partners, Community leaders, School representatives, Local media.	1 Year	P180,000

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		- Launch a media campaign on local radio and social media to promote child rights awareness.			
Engagement with NGOs for Recreational Activities	Enhance the quality and diversity of recreational and cultural activities offered.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Develop new partnerships with cultural and recreational NGOs.- Introduce cultural festivals and sports events.- Organize monthly community recreational days with diverse activities.- Set up permanent cultural and art exhibitions that involve local talents.	NGO representatives, Cultural committees, Sports clubs, Local artists.	1 Year	P200,000

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Understanding the root causes that bring children into conflict with the law (UNICEF).

Survival crimes and the link to child exploitation (ECPAT, 2017).

Support for children in conflict with the law (Kezia, 2017)

SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Annex “A” Letter to Respondents

Dear Respondents:

This researcher is a student in Doctor of Philosophy in Criminology (Ph.D. Crim)) at the Graduate School of Emilio Aguinaldo College Manila. As a pre-requisite for her graduation, she is required to conduct a research and to successfully defend the same in a panel of experts.

To comply with the requirements for graduation, she is now conducting a study, entitled: **“PROPOSED BARANGAY’S INTERVENTIONS PROGRAM FOR JUVENILE DELINQUENCY AND ITS PREVENTION PRACTICES TO BECOMING CHILDREN IN CONFLICT WITH THE LAW”**.

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Please answer completely this survey questionnaire and rest assured that all your responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Thank you very much for your kind cooperation in answering this survey questionnaire.

LEA SOLIS
Researcher

PART I. Assessment of the Respondents on the Juvenile Delinquency.

Please check (√) the space provided for corresponding to your best choice, using the following:

- 4- Strongly Agree (SA)
- 3- Agree
- 2- Disagree (DA)
- 1- Strongly Disagree (SDA)

Variables/Indicators	4	3	2	1
Children below the age of criminal responsibility				
1. Children below the age of criminal responsibility are recognized as still developing mentally, emotionally, and psychologically				
2. They may not fully understand the consequences of their actions or have the ability to make informed decisions				
3. More susceptible to exploitation and involvement in illegal activities				
4. Young children are highly impressionable and may be influenced by peer pressure, media, or adults in their environment				
5. They may engage in risky or delinquent behavior without fully comprehending the implications				
6. Children below the age of criminal responsibility may have limited cognitive abilities and judgment skills				
7. They may act impulsively without considering the consequences or fully understanding the moral and legal implications of their actions				
8. They rely heavily on adults, such as parents, guardians, or caregivers, for guidance, support, and supervision				
9. Potential for positive change and rehabilitation in these young individuals				
10. They are entitled to special safeguards and interventions aimed at promoting their well-being and preventing their involvement in criminal activities				

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Serious Crimes Committed by Children Who Are Exempt from Criminal Responsibility				
1. Serious crimes may involve acts of violence, including assault, physical fights, or even acts of homicide				
2. May engage in serious sexual offenses, such as rape or sexual assault				
3. Serious property crimes committed by children may include burglary, robbery, arson, or vandalism				
4. May participate in serious criminal activities, including drug trafficking, extortion, or organized violence				
5. Some children may illegally possess or use weapons, such as firearms or knives, to intimidate others or commit acts of violence				
6. Children may be influenced by peer pressure, family dynamics, or socioeconomic factors that contribute to involvement in drug-related activities				
7. May involve the possession, distribution, or trafficking of illegal drugs				
8. Repeatedly engage in serious criminal behavior may demonstrate a pattern of delinquency that requires comprehensive intervention strategies.				
9. Children may be exploited or coerced into participating in organized crime activities, such as human trafficking, smuggling, or gang operations.				
10. Children who commit serious crimes may themselves be victims of abuse, neglect, or trauma				
Repetition of offenses				
1. Repeat offenses often follow a pattern, with young offenders engaging in similar types of criminal behavior over time				
2. Lack of Effective Interventions, such as counseling, rehabilitation, or community service, some young offenders continue to reoffend				
3. Peer pressure and influence can play a significant role in the repetition of offenses among juvenile delinquents				
4. May be influenced by their peers to engage in criminal activities or may continue to associate with individuals involved in delinquent behavior				
5. Repeat offenders may have unmet needs, such as housing instability, substance abuse issues, mental health concerns, or lack of access to education and employment opportunities				
6. Young offenders may lack positive role models, support, and supervision within their family environment, making them more susceptible to engaging in criminal behavior.				
7. Involvement in criminal networks or gangs can perpetuate the cycle of delinquency among young offenders				
8. Substance abuse issues, including alcohol and drug addiction, can contribute to the repetition of offenses among juvenile delinquent				
9. Without adequate support, they may struggle to establish a positive and law-abiding lifestyle, increasing the likelihood of reoffending				
10. Structural and systemic factors, such as poverty, inequality, discrimination, and lack of access to justice, can contribute to the repetition of offenses among juvenile delinquents				

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Exploitation of Children for Commission of Crimes				
1. Exploited children often come from vulnerable backgrounds, including poverty, abuse, neglect, or family dysfunction				
2. They may lack access to basic needs such as education, healthcare, and protection, making them susceptible to manipulation and coercion by adults involved in criminal activities				
3. Children may be manipulated or coerced by adults, including family members, acquaintances, or criminal syndicates, into participating in illegal activities				
4. Children may be promised rewards, affection, or protection in exchange for their involvement, or threatened with violence or harm if they refuse				
5. Children may be exploited for forced labor, including activities such as drug trafficking, prostitution, begging, or petty theft				
6. They may be trafficked domestically or internationally, subjected to physical, emotional, or sexual abuse, and deprived of their rights and freedoms				
7. Children may be recruited or coerced into joining criminal gangs or syndicates, where they are used to carry out illegal activities such as drug trafficking, robbery, extortion, or violence				
8. With the rise of the internet and social media, children are increasingly vulnerable to online exploitation for the commission of crimes, including cybercrime, online fraud, child pornography, and online grooming by sexual predators				
9. Exploited children may be lured into dangerous situations through deceptive means or manipulated into sharing sensitive information or engaging in criminal activities online				
10. The exploitation of children for the commission of crimes can have profound and long-lasting effects on their physical, emotional, and psychological well-being				
Joint Parental Responsibility				
1. Parents or legal guardians have a legal obligation to provide care, guidance, and supervision to their children, including taking reasonable steps to prevent their involvement in delinquent behavior				
2. Joint parental responsibility emphasizes the shared accountability of both parents or legal guardians in addressing juvenile delinquency				
3. Parents are expected to serve as positive role models for their children, demonstrating responsible behavior, respect for the law, and ethical values				
4. Joint parental responsibility involves open communication and collaboration between parents or legal guardians in addressing the needs, challenges, and behaviors of their children				
5. Parents are responsible for establishing clear boundaries, rules, and expectations for their children's behavior, both at home and in the community				
6. Parents are expected to provide adequate supervision and monitoring of their children's activities, whereabouts, and social interactions				
7. Close supervision can help identify early warning signs of delinquent behavior and intervene effectively to address underlying issues				

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8. Joint parental responsibility includes active involvement in their children's education, including attending parent-teacher conferences, monitoring academic progress, and providing support for learning and skill development.				
9. Positive parental involvement in education can help prevent school-related delinquency and promote academic success				
10. Parents are expected to cooperate with law enforcement, juvenile justice authorities, and other relevant agencies in addressing juvenile delinquency issues involving their children				

PART III. Assessment on Barangay's Prevention Practices.

Variables/Indicators	4	3	2	1
Regular Monitoring of Children's Activities				
1. Organize and train community volunteers to monitor children's activities in the neighborhood				
2. Establish after-school programs that provide constructive and supervised activities for children				
3. Develop mentorship programs where responsible adults from the community are paired with at-risk children				
4. Encourage and support parents to be actively involved in their children's lives.				
5. Form youth councils that involve young people in the decision-making process regarding community activities				
6. Invest in and maintain recreational facilities such as parks, sports courts, and community centers where children can spend their free time in a safe environment				
7. Work with local schools to monitor attendance and performance				
Implementation of Curfew Hours				
1. Draft and enact a local ordinance that clearly defines curfew hours for minors				
2. Conduct awareness campaigns to educate the community about the curfew hours, the reasons for its implementation, and the benefits for the safety and well-being of children				
3. Conduct awareness campaigns to educate the community about the curfew hours, the reasons for its implementation, and the benefits for the safety and well-being of children				
4. Organize regular patrols by barangay tanods (local peacekeepers) and community volunteers during curfew hours				
5. Establish curfew centers where minors found violating curfew can be brought				
6. Establish curfew centers where minors found violating curfew can be brought				
7. Work with local schools, religious institutions, and youth organizations to reinforce the importance of curfew hours				
Community Based Rehabilitation Programs				
1. Provide comprehensive counseling services that address emotional, psychological, and behavioral issues				
2. Offer life skills training programs that equip children with essential skills for everyday life				
3. Establish educational support programs to help children who are struggling academically				

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4. Implement vocational training programs that provide children with practical skills that can lead to employment opportunities				
5. Develop peer mentoring and support groups where children can share their experiences and support each other.				
6. Engage children in community service projects that help them develop a sense of responsibility and contribution to their community.				
7. Offer sports and recreation programs to keep children physically active and engaged in positive activities				
Anti-Drug Campaigns				
1. Offer sports and recreation programs to keep children physically active and engaged in positive activities				
2. Conduct community outreach initiatives to raise awareness about the risks associated with drug use				
3. Train young people to become peer educators who can share information and experiences about drug prevention with their peers				
4. Offer workshops for parents to educate them about the signs of drug use, how to talk to their children about drugs, and ways to create a drug-free home environment				
5. Engaging students in creative projects can reinforce anti-drug messages				
6. Work with local law enforcement to conduct talks and seminars in schools and communities about the legal consequences of drug use and the importance of staying drug-free				
7. Provide alternative recreational activities and programs that keep children engaged and occupied				
Provisions of Livelihood Programs				
1. Develop programs that encourage and support entrepreneurship among community members				
2. Implement agricultural programs in rural barangays, such as backyard gardening, livestock raising, or aquaculture				
3. Encourage businesses to hire locally and offer internships or apprenticeships to youth, providing them with hands-on work experience				
4. Form community cooperatives that allow residents to pool their resources and work together on income-generating projects				
5. Integrate vocational education into the school curriculum, ensuring that students gain practical skills alongside their academic studies				
6. Organize livelihood fairs where community members can learn about different job opportunities				
7. Regularly monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of livelihood programs				
Youth Leadership Training				
1. Conduct regular workshops and seminars focused on leadership skills				
2. Establish mentorship programs where young leaders are paired with experienced mentors from the community				
3. Form youth councils or committees within the barangay that give young people a platform to voice their opinions and participate in decision-making processes				
4. Engage youth in community service projects where they can apply their leadership skills				

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5. Develop peer leadership programs that train young people to lead and support their peers				
6. Partner with local schools and universities to offer leadership training programs				
7. Partner with local schools and universities to offer leadership training programs				
Engagement in Sports ad Recreational Activities				
1. Establish organized sports leagues for various age groups and sports, such as basketball, soccer, volleyball, and track and field				
2. Invest in and maintain community sports facilities, such as basketball courts, soccer fields, swimming pools, and gyms				
3. Implement after-school sports programs that provide structured physical activities for children				
4. Organize sports tournaments and events that bring together participants from different schools and communities				
5. Partner with local sports clubs and organizations to offer specialized training and coaching				
6. Develop a variety of recreational activity programs beyond traditional sports				
7. Implement youth fitness programs that promote physical health and well-being				
Collaboration with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs)				
1. Establish formal partnerships with NGOs to implement prevention programs tailored to the needs of the community				
2. Work with NGOs to provide training and capacity-building workshops for barangay officials, parents, teachers, and community volunteers				
3. Collaborate with NGOs to develop and run youth empowerment programs that focus on leadership, life skills, and personal development				
4. Partner with NGOs to provide educational support, such as tutoring, scholarships, school supplies, and learning materials				
5. Work with health-focused NGOs to offer programs that address physical and mental health needs				
6. Collaborate on community outreach initiatives to raise awareness about issues such as child rights, drug abuse, and the importance of education				
7. Engage NGOs to organize recreational and cultural activities that keep children engaged in positive pursuits				

CURRICULUM VITAE

LEA NANKIL GALICIA-SOLIS, RMT, MAEd, PhD
Tel no. 546-3476
Cell no. 0928-555-0671

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

EMILIO AGUINALDO COLLEGE

ELECTRON COLLEGE OF TECHNICAL EDUCATION

Novaliches, Quezon City - Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education Major in Food Service Management, 2019

ARAULLO UNIVERSITY

Maharlika Highway, Barangay Bitas, Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija- Bachelor of Science in Criminology- 2018

NEW ERA UNIVERSITY

Central Quezon City - Bachelor of Laws (Juris Doctor) - 2017

METRO MANILA COLLEGE

Novaliches, Quezon City- Doctor of Philosophy- PhD in Development Education, 2014

DR. CARLOS LANTING COLLEGE

Sangandaan Novaliches Quezon City- Masteral Degree - MA in Education major in Administration and Supervision - 2001

FAR EASTERN UNIVERSITY

Claro M. Recto Manila- Bachelor of Science in Medical Technology- Academic Excellence Awardee- Academic Scholar - 1994-1998

STA LUCIA HIGH SCHOOL- Sta Lucia Novaliches Quezon City- Salutatorian- 1991-1994

SAN GABRIEL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL- Sta Lucia Novaliches Quezon City- Valedictorian- 1984-1990

LICENSURE EXAMINATION PASSED

PRC

1. *PRC Medical Technology Board Examination*
April 1998, UE Recto, Manila
2. *PRC Licensure Exam for Teacher (LET)*
August 2001, MLQU, Quiapo Manila

TESDA

1. *Health Care Service NC II*
February 2011
2. *Driving NC II*
October 2011
3. *Front Office NCII*

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4. *Bookkeeping NCIII*
5. *Trainers Methodology*

WORK EXPERIENCE

NOVALICHES DISTRICT HOSPITAL (Government Hospital)

Clinical Laboratory Department
Medical Technologist
2004-2005

DON QUINTIN PAREDES HIGH SCHOOL (DepEd School)

Chemistry Teacher
2002

DR. CARLOS LANTING COLLEGE MEDTECH DEPARTMENT (Private College)

College Chemistry / Bio-Chem Instructor
1999-2002

NOVALICHES GENERAL HOSPITAL (Private Hospital)

Chief Medical Technologist
1998-2000

BUSINESSES (Solis Group of Companies)

1. Electron College of Technical Education
2. Philippine Lyceum of Saint Dominicque
3. Children of Mary Immaculate College (International School)
4. Galicia – Solis Medical Laboratories and Polyclinic
5. Solis Construction & Design
6. Solis Mansion Hotel & Private Resort
7. Solis Mansion Beachfront Hotel and Resort
8. Alaenis Place Salon and Spa
9. Café La Escuela
10. Blue Crystal Events Place and Catering Services

AFFILIATIONS

1. **ROYAL INSTITUTION OF SINGAPORE**
Honorary President – Medical Technologists
2. **ROTARY CLUB INTERNATIONAL**
Past President
3. **PHILIPPINE AIR FORCE**

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Reservist – Sergeant

4. ASSOCIATION OF TECHNICAL SCHOOLS IN THE PHILIPPINES

National Secretary

5. ASSOCIATION OF TESDA ACCREDITED SCHOOL OWNERS – QUEZON CITY

Vice President

6. ASSOCIATION OF DEPED RECOGNIZED SCHOOLS

Board Member

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read "L. Solis", on a light gray rectangular background.

DR. LEA GALICIA SOLIS